

**DETERMINANTS OF PUBLIC SECTOR EMPLOYMENT
AMONG STEM PROFESSIONALS: EVIDENCE FROM
GHANA**

BY

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DEDICATION

This thesis is dedicated to my father, Joseph A. Quarchie.

ABSTRACT

Ghana's digital transformation agenda requires more technical skills from its public sector, yet STEM graduates disproportionately flow toward private employment, leaving government institutions chronically understaffed in data analytics, engineering, and information systems. This study investigates the determinants of public sector employment among STEM professionals in Ghana by examining the demographic, socio-economic, perceptual, motivational, and structural factors shaping both career intentions and realised employment outcomes. The study uses Human Capital Theory, Labour Market Segmentation Theory, Labour Market Matching Theory, Public Service Motivation Theory, and Expectancy Theory, to conduct a quantitative cross-sectional survey design administered to 312 respondents comprising final-year STEM students, masters students and recent graduates from Ashesi University, Berekuso. Five binary logistic regression models are estimated across student and graduate sub-samples to identify the significant predictors of public sector career choice at both the intention and realisation stages.

The results reveal that gender significantly predicts public sector career intention, with female students more likely to intend government employment, while a directional reversal at the graduate stage, where male graduates are more likely to actually be employed in the public sector which points to structural barriers preventing female intentions from converting into realised employment outcomes. Perceived skill-job alignment emerges as the strongest predictor of public sector intent among students, and occupational prestige and effort-reward expectancy perceptions are also significant positive drivers. Most unexpectedly, public service motivation is consistently and significantly negatively associated with public sector outcomes across all model specifications, suggesting that highly motivated graduates redirect their civic values toward NGOs and international organisations rather than the civil service. The study concludes that STEM underrepresentation in Ghana's public sector reflects a complex interaction of structural recruitment barriers, weak skill-alignment communication, and an institutional culture that fails to capture the motivation of the graduates most disposed toward public service, and proposes five evidence-based recommendations directed at the Public Services Commission, government ministries, and university career development offices.

Keywords: STEM professionals, public sector employment, labour market matching, public service motivation, binary logistic regression, Ghana.

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ACRONYMS

Acronym	Full Definition
AME	Average Marginal Effect
GPA	Grade Point Average
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
LLR	Log-Likelihood Ratio
LMM	Labour Market Matching
MMDA	Metropolitan, Municipal and District Assembly
NCSES	National Center for Science and Engineering Statistics
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
NITA	National Information Technology Agency
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PNDCL	Provisional National Defense Council Law
PSM	Public Service Motivation
SD	Standard Deviation
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics
TVET	Technical and Vocational Education and Training
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) disciplines are increasingly shaping the global knowledge economy and driving innovation-led growth. In Ghana, the expansion of STEM education has become central to national strategies such as the Digital Acceleration Project (2022) and the National Science, Technology and Innovation Policy (2021), which highlight the need for skilled professionals to modernize governance and improve public service delivery.

Despite these efforts, recent evidence shows that only 26.15% of TVET graduates, a significant components of the STEM workforce, pursue jobs in the government sector, while the majority prefer private sector (54.62%) and many engage in self-employment (44.62%), which shows that most people in this field prefer these two career paths instead of government jobs (Ababio et al., 2024). The imbalance between public sector work and private sector work creates a danger for Ghana because it will now need digital capabilities that include data analytics, information systems and engineering.

The state's need for STEM personnel arises from the growing complexity of governance, the adoption of digital technologies, and the demand for evidence-based policymaking. Generally, there are not enough digitally skilled professionals in ministries and agencies in Ghana to lead the digital transformation and to be the source of the digital innovation ecosystem for national and regional development (World Bank, 2022). Understanding what determines the attraction or lack thereof of STEM professionals to public service is therefore a matter of national importance.

One potential source of such talent is graduates from top universities that train STEM professionals. Ashesi University, a major private university in Ghana, provides STEM programs which include Engineering, Computer Science, and Management Information Systems. The university produces graduates who possess both technical skills and the ability to lead with strong ethical standards. The study on how demographic factors and academic performance affects STEM graduate career paths from Ashesi University will provide essential information about upcoming job market developments which will help create evidence-based policy interventions.

1.2 Problem Statement

Public sector agencies across several nations are faced with challenges in securing and maintaining STEM professionals who are essential for their digital governance and technological advancements and modern public service operations. Public sector organizations in advanced technological environments demonstrate through their evidence that their recruitment processes face major impediments because of their slow and rigid systems together with their outdated job classifications and their limited hiring options and their uncompetitive salary structures (Zolak et al., 2025). The result leads to government agencies maintaining extended periods without filling their essential technology positions which damages institutional capabilities while hindering digital transformation initiatives (CCS Global Tech, 2025). The existing challenges demonstrate that the labour market functions fail to establish proper connections between public sector demand for STEM skills and available skills while creating uncertainty about how employment intentions transform into actual public sector careers.

In Ghana, while there is a growing policy emphasis on recruiting STEM professionals into the public sector, little is known about the determinants that influence their employment choices. Studies on graduate employability in Ghana (Segbenya et al., 2023) have focused mainly on private-sector readiness and skill alignment but have rarely examined why the public sector attracts fewer STEM graduates.

It is also unclear how individual intentions align with actual employment outcomes and whether existing institutional incentives support these intentions. Furthermore, the determinants of public employment among STEM professionals have not been studied through empirical because researchers have not assessed that in relation to the state's demand for technical expertise.

This study addresses this gap by identifying the factors influencing STEM professionals' engagement in public employment and assessing how career intentions correspond to realized employment outcomes. The research aims to deliver evidence-based findings which will help match STEM workforce availability with the state's changing human capital requirements.

1.3 Research Objectives

General Objectives

To identify the determinants influencing public sector employment among STEM professionals in Ghana.

Specific Objectives

- To examine demographic, socio-economic, and academic factors affecting STEM professionals' participation in public employment.
- To assess how perceptions of salary, job security, innovation, and prestige influence employment sector choices.
- To evaluate the alignment between STEM graduates' career intentions and their actual employment outcomes.
- To propose policy recommendations for improving STEM recruitment and retention within Ghana's public sector.

1.4 Research Question

What determines STEM professionals' participation in public sector employment in Ghana?

1.5 Significance of the Study

The study contributes to academic and policy discussions on workforce planning and public administration reform in Ghana by providing empirical evidence on the individual, socioeconomic, and institutional factors influencing public sector employment decisions among STEM professionals. The findings offer guides to government agencies looking forward to design recruitment and retention strategies aligned with Ghana's digital transformation agenda, especially by highlighting how perceptions of salary, job security, innovation opportunities, and career expectations shape sectoral preferences.

In addition, the research informs policy planners about the link between STEM graduate employment outcomes and public sector human resource needs. By investigating the relationship between career intentions and actual employment paths, the study clarifies structural and motivational factors that are affecting the attraction of STEM talent into government jobs. The findings highlight areas where university preparation and labour market expectations intersect, thereby contributing to improved labour market matching and strengthened human capital development in Ghana.

1.6 Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to examine the factors influencing STEM students' career intentions and graduates' employment outcomes, with a specific focus on the likelihood of choosing or working in the public sector. It aims to identify how demographic, motivational, and socio-economic variables shape these decisions.

1.7 Object of the Study

The object of the study is the process of career choice and employment outcomes among individuals with STEM backgrounds, particularly the determinants that influence selection into the public sector versus other sectors.

1.8 Subject of the Study

The subject of the study consists of final-year undergraduate students, master's students, and recent STEM graduates, including those forming career intentions and those already employed.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Understanding why STEM graduates choose or avoid the public sector requires us to think carefully about the people making these decisions, the institutional environment in which they make them, and the broader forces that shape what options even appear available. This review builds that picture in layers. It begins by defining who STEM professionals are and why their career trajectories matter, then situates the discussion within Ghana's public sector and its evolving human capital demands. It examines what the evidence says about how graduates experience the transition from education to employment, both in Ghana and across comparable developing-country contexts. And it draws on a set of interrelated theoretical perspectives not as a checklist, but as lenses that help make sense of patterns that the empirical literature alone cannot fully explain. The review concludes by synthesising the specific determinants of sectoral career choice that will guide the hypotheses and analytical framework of this study.

2.1 Who Are STEM Professionals, and Why Does Their Sectoral Placement Matter?

Before asking where STEM graduates go after university, it is worth asking what we mean by STEM and who counts as a STEM professional. The question matters because the answer shapes both who is studied and what findings can be generalised. Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) is sometimes described as a meta-discipline a framework that integrates distinct knowledge domains into a coherent whole oriented toward problem-solving and innovation (Morrison, 2006). UNESCO defines STEM as encompassing the disciplines that drive innovation and address global challenges (UNESCO, 2025), while the U.S. National Center for Science and Engineering Statistics defines STEM professionals as individuals who utilise science, engineering, mathematics,

and technology in carrying out the primary functions of their jobs (NCSES, 2024). These definitions, though institutionally varied, converge on a common thread: STEM is defined by what practitioners do with their knowledge, not merely by the degree they hold.

Within the STEM pipeline, three distinct groups are typically distinguished. STEM students are those still enrolled in formal education within these disciplines, still forming career intentions and professional identities (Dou et al., 2019). The STEM graduates represent all who finished their higher education studies and are now ready to enter the workforce where their career goals will start to separate from their actual career path. Skrentny and Lewis (2022) define a STEM graduate as anyone who earned their first bachelor's degree in one of the four core STEM fields. STEM professionals, by contrast, are those actively applying technical skills within an occupational context, whether in the public service, private industry, or entrepreneurship. Distinguishing among these groups is more than definitional housekeeping: it is analytically essential, because the factors that shape an intention during final year of study may differ meaningfully from those that determine where someone actually ends up working three years later.

The sectoral placement of STEM graduates has attracted growing policy attention because the returns to STEM education are not automatic, they depend on where that education is deployed. Research by Autor (2014) demonstrates that STEM skills command growing wage premiums in private-sector labour markets, particularly in technology-intensive industries. At the same time, public institutions are increasingly dependent on STEM competencies to manage complex governance challenges. The OECD (2023) reports that states worldwide, including those of its member countries, face serious difficulties in finding sufficiently educated technical workers to support their digital transformation projects. This problem is even more pronounced in countries with lower income levels. There, the demand for the government to hire technical experts is very high, at the same time, the government often does not have the funds to offer a salary and a career that can compete with those of the private sector. Ghana is a very good example of this situation, as the different parts of this paper will reveal.

2.2 Public Sector Employment in Ghana: Structure, Demand, and the Digital Imperative

What does public sector employment actually mean in the Ghanaian context, and what kinds of skills does it currently require? These questions deserve more than a passing

answer, because the attractiveness of public sector work and the barriers to entering it are partly a product of how that sector is institutionally organised.

Public service in Ghana is broadly understood as the set of activities carried out by government institutions to meet the collective needs of society (Duguit, 1922). Within this, the civil service refers specifically to the permanent administrative and professional staff employed by the state to advise on and implement public policy (Idode, 1989). Institutionally, Ghana's public administration operates through ministries, departments and agencies established under the Civil Service Act (PNDCL 327); state-owned enterprises under constitutional and statutory provisions; and local government authorities created under the 1992 Constitution and the Local Governance Act, 2016 (Act 936). The key institutions are formed by the Ministry of Finance, Ministry of Communications and Digitalisation, Ghana Revenue Authority and the National Information Technology Agency (NITA). Metropolitan, Municipal, and District Assemblies (MMDAs) take public administration a step further by involving the local or community level, thereby spreading governance down to the delivery of services to communities (Antwi-Boasiako, 2010).

Employment in this system is managed by uniform wage levels, recruitment through a central authority, and promotion mainly depending on seniority, written tests, and the availability of vacancies. The system creates equal pay between workers but it prevents organizations from using performance metrics to determine pay differences and it creates challenges for organizations to acquire employees with advanced specialized technical skills (Ayee 2008). Recruitment timelines can be protracted, and job classifications may not map cleanly onto the specialised competencies that STEM graduates bring. These structural features are not unique to Ghana Zolak et al. (2025) document similar rigidities across public administration systems in Eastern Europe but they are particularly consequential in a context where the public sector is simultaneously trying to attract exactly the kind of talent that private and multinational employers are actively competing for.

What makes this tension particularly urgent in Ghana is the scale of the country's digital transformation agenda. Initiatives which include the e-Government agenda, the Digital Address System, the National Science, Technology and Innovation Policy (2021), and the World Bank-supported Digital Acceleration Project (2022) together signal a strategic commitment to technology-enabled governance. These reforms require government institutions to attract professionals who are trained in data analytics, information systems, engineering, and quantitative modelling to design, manage, and sustain digital infrastructure. According to Hood and Margetts (2007) digital-era governance means

public institutions will need to develop new skills because it replaces outdated bureaucratic competencies with technical and analytical abilities. Berman et al. (2021) also contend that an effective public management in a technologically evolving context particularly will depend on attracting personnel with these competencies. The World Bank (2022) has noted that Ghana struggles with a shortage of digitally skilled professionals in its ministries and agencies, this gap in turn limits the very policy reforms that the country prioritises.

The cost of this gap extends beyond delayed timelines. Castells (2011) argues in his analysis of the networked information society that states which lack adequate technological capabilities will experience permanent exclusion from the digital global economy. The civil service in Ghana faces cybersecurity threats and data management problems and missing STEM expertise which leads to trouble developing evidence-based policies and digital public services take longer to implement. Schultz (1961) made the point decades ago that investments in education generate returns only when human capital is effectively deployed within productive sectors. The public sector loses the economic benefits from national technical education investments when STEM graduates choose to work in private companies or start their own businesses or move to other countries. The main research question of this thesis explores which factors create this pattern and which strategies might redirect it.

2.3 The Graduate Labour Market in Ghana: Transitions, Mismatches, and Sectoral Competition

To understand what leads STEM graduates to their outcomes, it is necessary to consider the larger labour market conditions under which they choose their paths. The graduate labour market in Ghana has grown significantly over the last 20 years. Enrolment in tertiary education rose from only 4% of the population in the age group to 17% by 2020 (World Bank data), due primarily to the rise in public and private universities. However, this increase in graduates has not been accompanied by a corresponding increase in the creation of good formal jobs. Hence, graduate unemployment and underemployment are still major structural features of the Ghanaian economy (Segbenya et al., 2023). Many graduates can only find employment after a long time, and a large proportion settle for jobs that do not use their qualifications or even their field of study, which is a sort of skills mismatch with side effects both for individuals and overall productivity.

Both the public sector and private sector are competing for the small section of graduates that have technical knowledge, although the battle for such scarce resources has

been far from equal. Public sectors used to be a dominant source of employment for university graduates in Ghana. Administration, education and technical services are common public sectors where graduates can secure employment. Private sectors has become an appealing choice to the job seekers due to faster recruitments, merit pay and knowledge acquisition in cutting edge developments (Fox et al., 2016; Edwards et al., 2021). Specifically, for graduates in engineering and information systems, the private sector more often than not offers a better scope for advancement based on merit and skills development opportunities that one can hardly get in the existence of public sector hierarchical structures.

The National Service Scheme transition data shows this pattern because many graduates complete their mandatory service in public institutions but their public sector employment ends when they finish their service. In Ghana the employability outcome appears strongly related to practical experience and internship because according to Winful (2023), the students who have relationships in the industry while being at school seem to utilize these connections to secure jobs in the private sector rather than public sector positions. According to Segbenya et al (2023), three factors are taken into account when Ghanaian university students make their career choices. These are students' perception of employers' expectations and employers' anticipated salary and job security. While majority of Ghanaian students choose the private sector as it provides best opportunity for them.

The STEM pipeline in Ghana adds a further dimension to this picture. Ghana has expanded tertiary STEM programmes as part of its educational system to support its technological advancement and modernization goals which has increased student enrollment in engineering, computer science, and information systems programs. The distribution of STEM graduates across sectors remains skewed because ICT graduates prefer to work at private technology firms and start-ups and multinational corporations which offer better opportunities for innovation and higher pay (Amankwah-Amoah, 2016). Public institutions cannot attract top-performing graduates from these fields because they lack competitive salaries and flexible work options which most high-achieving students expect from their jobs. Public administration capacity research in Ghana reveals digital governance skills gaps and data management skills gaps and technical analysis skills gaps which show that civil service needs exceed what the government can attract to its workforce (Fobih, 2020).

The African context supports the generalization of these trends. The continent experiences widespread unemployment and underemployment among young graduates

who completed tertiary education because their educational systems produce graduates who lack the skills required by the job market (Iwara, 2025). The structural issues which include, among others, limited availability of quality STEM education, ineffective curriculum-industry alignment, and insufficiently strong colleges' linkages with employers, further worsen the problem (Ege and Erdil, 2023). The domestic public sectors face a major problem from brain drainage because trained STEM professionals who cannot find good jobs in their home countries now seek work opportunities abroad or through international remote work (UNESCO, 2024). According to United Nations (2025) Africa is estimated to require tens of millions of people with higher digital skills by 2030, and there is thus an acute need to tackle the issue of graduate output as against employment absorptive capacity in public sector.

2.4 From Intention to Outcome: The Career Transition of STEM Graduates

It directly relates to labor market institutions and to the quality of career assistance services to the graduates and structural obstacles which inhibit them from acting according to their wishes.

Career intentions refer to an individual's expressed plans, preferences, or aspirations regarding future employment or occupational pathways (Ajzen, 1991). They are formed during the period of education and shaped by academic experiences, exposure to professional networks, labour market information, and socio-economic background (Lent et al., 1994). For STEM students and graduates, career intentions often reflect preferences for specific sectors based on perceptions of salary, innovation potential, job security, and professional growth. These intentions serve as an important early indicator of how human capital is likely to be allocated across sectors but they are not deterministic.

The outcomes in employment on the other hand, mean the actual employment posts, industries and career paths that individuals are ultimately employed in after leaving the institution. The literature on graduate transitions notes that actual outcomes is not only determined by academic qualifications, but also by the acquisition of vocational competencies and the efficiency of internships, as well as the structures of opportunities provided by institutions (Siivonen et al. 2023). As demonstrated by Garwe (2020) the learning of core competencies at university, for instance, autonomy, the ability to lead a group and to apply skills autonomously predict higher employment outcomes and starting salaries and hence what a graduate does during university learning is as important as the

actual learning process itself. Likewise, Brown and Lent (2019) argue that efficiency of internships is an effective means to transfer classroom learning to actual workplace settings thus enhancing both confidence and involvement.

When students' expectations of the career and their employment is consistent then students will report greater satisfaction and identity coherency in the long term career (Lennox, 2025). Conversely, where they are mismatched, job dissatisfaction and a loss of human capital are the outcomes of the individual and the society. Career mismatches are most often structural, reflecting poor links between education and the job market, inadequate career guidance and a lack of job opportunities in preferred fields (Siivonen et al. 2023). Structural factors within the public sector in Ghana may specifically relate to a non-transparent recruitment process, lack of knowledge about career prospects within the public sector for STEM graduates, and absence of strong internship/mentoring relationships between the university and public sector institutions. Measuring the size and character of the intention-outcome gap for STEM graduates within Ghana therefore does not only hold theoretical significance, but also practical value; highlighting the precise location where policy can intervene.

2.5 Making Sense of Sector Choice: Theoretical Perspectives

The empirical patterns described above raise a deeper question: why, exactly, do some graduates choose the public sector while others do not? The answer cannot be read off from income data alone, nor can it be reduced to individual preference. The selection of sectors is determined by a complex interrelation of structural inducements, institutional structures, individual differences, and individual values; a complex phenomenon that demands a variety of perspectives to provide any light on it. This part is guided by five related perspectives, although not for the purpose of constructing a binding structure, but a cumulative knowledge base.

2.5.1 Returns to Education and the Logic of Sector Choice

A natural starting point for understanding sector choice is the question of economic returns. If individuals invest in education, particularly in technically demanding fields, where do they expect that investment to pay off most? This is the question at the heart of what economists call Human Capital Theory. According to Becker (1964) education and training can be thought of as an investment which will increase people's productiveness and consequently the amount of income they receive. This notion was developed by Mincer (1974) who illustrated that earnings through the life-cycle are shaped by formal schooling

as well as on the job training. Within this perspective, career choices reflect calculations about anticipated returns: individuals weigh up expected earnings, promotion prospects, and opportunities for professional development across the options available to them, and select the path that best maximises their lifetime returns.

For STEM graduates, this logic produces a clear prediction: if private-sector employers offer substantially higher wages or faster career growth for technical expertise, rational graduates will gravitate toward private employment. Most of the empirical evidence supports this forecast. In tech-intense industries, wage premia for STEM jobs are rising in response to market competition and profit-driven forces (Autor, 2014) In many settings, government employees with skills that command high salaries in the private sector fare poorly in terms of compensation (Edwards et al., 2021 on the federal government vs the private sector; Hino and Ranis, 2014 on the Ghana public sector); migration from the public sector to entrepreneurship or private enterprise has been linked to these differentials (Edwards et al., 2021; Palacios and Clemens, 2013).

Yet the human capital framework also points to an important caveat. Perceived returns matter as much as actual returns, and perceptions are not always accurate. STEM students may overestimate private sector earnings, underestimate the value of public sector benefits such as pension security and job stability, or have limited information about career progression pathways within the civil service. This gap between perception and reality is directly relevant to the design of recruitment and retention strategies and to the measurement strategy of this study.

2.5.2 The Structure of Sectors: Why Institutional Differences Shape Career Trajectories

Human Capital Theory treats sector choice largely as a function of individual calculation. But career trajectories are also shaped by the structural features of the sectors themselves, features that are not determined by any individual graduate's preferences. The Labor Market Segmentation Theory (Doeringer and Piore, 1971) is the primary theory available for the explanation of structural disparities like those aforementioned, questioning the neoclassical assumption of an integrated competitive labor market. Instead, it argues that labour markets are structurally divided into distinct segments, each governed by different institutional rules, wage-setting mechanisms, and mobility opportunities.

In classical formulations, these segmentations of the market have been described in terms of primary and secondary. Primary segments of the market were perceived to offer

more skill development, career movement, and wage progression; whereas secondary segments were characterised by lower pay and weaker work conditions and mobility. Building on the above formulations, Reich et al., (1973) emphasized how structural/institutional factors (arrangements and sectors) have shaped career paths that individuals experience beyond the human capital explanation. In the context of the public-private sector, we see that the public sector appears to reflect a more or less a primary labor market, in terms of job security, regulation and seniority-based promotion, although wage growth and incentives for high-level specific technical skills may be less than that found in the private STEM sector (seen more as a more dynamic, higher-pay off segment, providing performance incentives and high returns for the technically-trained, and featuring much higher rates of career advancement).

This structural differentiation provides an important theoretical explanation for why STEM graduates whose skills command high market value and who may particularly value opportunities for innovation and rapid advancement disproportionately favour private employment. Empirical studies show that high-skilled workers frequently sort into sectors that maximise both pecuniary and professional returns, particularly when private-sector wages substantially exceed public-sector compensation (Gindling, 1991; Bender, 2003). In Ghana, this dynamic is vividly reflected in Ghana's burgeoning private digital and technology sector, in which a reward structure emphasizing performance, employment flexibility, and the opportunity to work on a novel set of challenges can retain a cohort of graduates that is difficult for the public sector to retain. Hence, the theory provides two straightforward predictions for this study: perception of higher salary growth and perceived opportunities for innovation in the private sector will have a negative impact on the decision to select public sector employment and perceptions of job security and employment stability in the public sector will have a positive impact.

2.5.3 Search Frictions, Mismatches, and the Efficiency of Recruitment

Even when graduates want to enter the public sector and the public sector wants to hire them, the match may not happen or may happen poorly. Labour Market Matching Theory, associated with the Nobel Prize-winning work of Mortensen and Pissarides (1994), directs attention to the frictions and inefficiencies in the process of connecting job seekers with employers. In the classical matching framework, the efficiency of this process determines how well individuals find jobs that fit both their educational level and their occupational needs. Under conditions of imperfect information, search costs or structural frictions where

matching is not efficient, job vacancies and unemployment can co-exist, workers may be in the wrong job or not working to their full potential.

Two distinct but related concepts are of importance here: Education-occupation mismatch. This occurs when a worker's level of education does not match the requirements of the job that they occupy, and takes two forms: overeducation where the worker has higher qualifications than are required by the job or undereducation (McGuinness, 2006); overeducation causes both wages penalties and job dissatisfaction; while the two forms of mismatch suggest that both labour markets are not matching their educated work force properly (Montt, 2017). Another similar concept is sector match, a case where field of study does not match field of employment for example: an engineering graduate working as a retail management, or a graduate in computer sciences where technical knowledge and experience could not be applied to work (Ege and Erdil, 2023).

In terms of this study, the theory of matching leads to one of a series of questions: "Do STEM graduates in Ghana have knowledge about the availability of public sector jobs in their respective fields?" Do they perceive the recruitment process as transparent and their skills as well-aligned with public sector requirements? Are there institutional frictions centralised approval systems, protracted hiring timelines, poorly designed job descriptions that prevent motivated graduates from successfully entering the civil service even when they want to? These questions are directly measurable through the questionnaire and constitute one of the analytical threads running through the study.

2.5.4 Beyond Wages: Intrinsic Motivation and the Pull of Public Service

The frameworks considered so far share a broadly economic logic: they explain sector choice in terms of wages, returns, structural incentives, and matching efficiency. But they leave something important unexplained. There are graduates who choose the public sector even when private alternatives would pay more and there are public servants who stay in government roles despite attractive outside options. What motivates them?

There is an explanation for this which can be found in Public Service Motivation (PSM) Theory by Perry and Wise (1990). PSM Theory asserts that some individuals have an predisposition towards motives associated with public institutions and organizations and a devotion to public values, civic and communal obligation and general welfare which inherently attracts them to work in the public sector irrespective of any pay. Perry and Wise (1990) define Public Service Motivation as a multi-dimensional construct consisting of attraction to public policymaking, commitment to public interest, compassion and sacrifice.

Perry (1996) later operationalised these dimensions into measurable scales that have been widely used in subsequent empirical research.

The empirical record on PSM is extensive and largely consistent. Higher amounts of public service motivation also correlate with preferences for government jobs and organizational commitment in government agencies and low intentions to quit (Vandenabeele, 2007; Brewer et al., 2000). Importantly, these effects hold even after controlling for extrinsic rewards: PSM operates through intrinsic channels that are conceptually distinct from salary or career progression calculations. For STEM graduates in Ghana, PSM may take a particularly salient form: commitment to national development, the desire to contribute to digital governance transformation, and a sense of professional responsibility toward strengthening public institutions in a context where those institutions are still being built. Where such motivations are strong, graduates may be willing to accept public sector positions even when private alternatives offer higher immediate financial returns. The study therefore expects PSM to be a significant positive predictor of public sector employment intentions and outcomes and its measurement through a validated Likert-scale instrument is a central feature of the research design.

2.5.5 Perceived Probability, Anticipated Reward, and the Decision to Act

The last theoretical contribution deals with an implicit and pragmatic question: is there an individual that is truly intrinsically inclined towards public service and that also perceives the public sector as structurally appealing will ever pursue the path of recruitment, unless they feel that recruitment will be possible and will bring appropriate rewards? That is exactly the point of Expectancy Theory, as formulated by Vroom (1964). The theory identifies three core components of motivation: expectancy (the belief that effort will lead to successful performance), instrumentality (the belief that performance will lead to outcomes or rewards), and valence (the value placed on those expected rewards). Motivation to pursue a particular career path depends on all three: a graduate who wants to work in government but believes the recruitment process is opaque, that strong performance will go unrecognised, or that the rewards on offer are inadequate, will be demotivated regardless of their underlying preferences.

Applying this to STEM workers in Ghana, Expectancy Theory would hypothesize that the barriers that STEM professionals perceive for joining the public service, namely the opaque nature of entry requirements, lack of recognition for performance, and the weak link between inputs and career progression, would lessen the motivational power for

pursuing public service careers. On the other hand, job seekers who see a plausible future path to success and who consider the career rewards adequate would see public service careers as attainable and fulfilling. Porter and Lawler (1968) provided an alternative model that, although it follows the logic of Vroom, focuses attention on both the instrumental and intrinsic rewards that are associated with outcomes and their contribution to job satisfaction and performance, and reiterates the premise that an individual's career choice is influenced by the subjective appraisal of the total reward structures rather than simple comparisons in salary levels. Here, proxies for perception of transparency in entry processes, anticipation of rewarded input, and equity in performance-reward coupling represent the expectancy-instrumentality-valence framework.

2.6 What the Global Evidence Shows: Sector Choice Across Contexts

Having established the theoretical lenses through which sector choice can be understood, it is worth examining what the empirical literature across different national contexts reveals about the factors that actually predict where graduates end up. The global evidence is broadly consistent with the theoretical framework developed above, while also highlighting the importance of national and institutional context.

Research in Europe and North America continually reports that there are several job differences between the public and private sectors, where it really matters for graduates. Analyzing public-private employment gaps across 22 European countries and the United States Fenizia et al. (2024) reports differences vary significantly between places, although there are public-sector pay premia in some European countries and negative pay premia in the US the former consistently outperforms the private sector in job security and work-life balance although it lacks the pay-for-performance incentives in the latter. Holum et al. (2024) show in a comparison of business students in Norway and Poland, both country choice of public or private sector jobs are influenced by preferences towards job security, social contribution and professional development although the influence of country is pronounced. This set of preferences from the public sector, regarding job security and contribution to society is, according to Opstad (2025), also found among the Scandinavian students. Midttun (2007) shows that among Norwegian medical specialists, differences in risk tolerance and work values often outweigh income comparisons in determining sector choice.

Cross-national research on personality and sector choice adds a further dimension. Dufault et al. (2023) note that agreeableness, conscientiousness, and pro-social

responsibility orientation predict the individual interest to work in the public sector, more specifically for the female individuals, what has immediate relevance for the gender hypothesis we are considering in this research. These results suggest that sector choice cannot be reduced to structural incentives alone; individual dispositional characteristics mediate the relationship between perceived job attributes and career decisions.

Also, international literature contains helpful insights into policy lever changes sector preferences. Reforms in recruitment and selection, increasing transparency and decreasing procedural costs have been effective in attracting technically competent graduates to the public sector (Zolak et al., 2025). Compensation reforms: increased performance-based compensation and/or premium wages for scarce technical jobs have successfully narrowed the gap in pay to the private sector and made public sector more competitive. Employer branding campaigns, aimed at communicating the mission, value and career opportunities available in public administration, have been proved effective to change graduate perspectives and behaviors (CCS Global Tech, 2025).

2.7 Determinants of Sectoral Career Choice: Synthesising the Evidence

Drawing together the theoretical perspectives and empirical literature reviewed above, it is possible to identify a set of specific determinants that consistently emerge as predictors of sectoral career choice. These determinants operate at multiple levels, individual, socio-economic, perceptual, and structural and their interaction shapes both career intentions and realised outcomes.

On an individual level, variables such as age, gender and academic background can affect sector preferences through a number of routes. For example, gender is reported to influence occupational preferences by means of social norms, work-life balance expectations and occupational stereotypes (Eagly and Wood 2012; Dufault et al., 2023). For example, women may have an increased appreciation for the work-life balance and job security within public service or might be subject to different social pressures about appropriate careers. Similarly, gender and academic experience are likely to influence career maturity and access to occupational networks, both of which would have an effect on the quality of career information available to the graduates making the sectoral decision. Academic performance, captured through GPA, may also signal competitiveness for high-paying private sector roles and thereby affect sector choice through the lens of expected returns.

Another aspect that is worth considering is socio-economic status. Income of parents, their jobs and therefore their propensity to risk can have implications in sectoral choice and risk preferences; people from poorer background may want a safer, stable job (public sector) more (Ng et al., 2005). However, access to grants or loans will release graduates from monetary burdens and allow them to pick public sector without the financial pressure of a lower earning (in terms of public sector) job over the higher earning one (in terms of private sector). Similarly, social capital derived from family relationships can have an impact on access to specific information related to sectors (Lin, 1999; Bourdieu, 1986). These socio-economic factors operate as background conditions that structure the opportunity set within which individual career choices are made.

Perceptions of sector attributes emerge consistently as among the strongest proximate predictors of sector choice. How graduates evaluate the salary competitiveness, job security, innovation potential, and occupational prestige of public versus private employment shapes their preferences more directly than objective differences in sector characteristics precisely because it is perceptions, not objective realities, that individuals act on. It is accepted that potential employees will consider the expected rewards across different industries in their career decisions (Vroom, 1964; Porter and Lawler, 1968), and that comparisons will be affected by the availability, accuracy and quality of information. Public sector employment is well known for its better employment security but poorer pay increases, and this trade-off will be perceived differently by people depending on risk attitude, life-phase, and financial requirements (Perry and Wise, 1990). For STEM graduates specifically, whose skills create attractive outside options, perceived innovation opportunities and professional recognition may be especially influential, a finding that aligns with Becker's (1964) insight that individuals with higher human capital accumulation are more sensitive to differences in the quality of the career development opportunities on offer.

Finally, the intention-behaviour relationship itself is a determinant of realised outcomes. The theory of planned behaviour (Ajzen, 1991) suggests that career intentions are shaped by attitudes toward a behaviour, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control, the degree to which individuals believe they can successfully carry out the intended action. Even graduates who intend to enter the public sector may not realise that intention if they perceive recruitment barriers as prohibitive, if they lack information about available vacancies, or if their skill set is not well-matched to public sector requirements as they understand them. Examining both intentions (among students) and realised sector (among

graduates) is therefore essential for capturing the full complexity of the career decision process and for identifying where, specifically, the transition from intention to outcome breaks down.

2.8 Research Gaps

The literature reviewed in this section establishes a rich foundation for the empirical analysis that follows. It shows that STEM graduates in Ghana operate in a labour market characterised by rapid expansion, persistent mismatch, and intensifying competition between public and private employers for a limited pool of technically skilled workers. Ghana's public sector has urgent and growing need for STEM talent to support digital governance transformation, but faces structural disadvantages in compensation, recruitment efficiency, and career development opportunities that weaken its competitive position. The global and African evidence suggests that sectoral career choice is shaped by a combination of structural incentives, individual characteristics, socio-economic background, perceptions of sector attributes, and intrinsic motivational orientations with significant variation across national and institutional contexts.

Several important gaps remain. First, while considerable evidence exists on graduate employability in Ghana generally, there is a paucity of empirical studies specifically examining the determinants of public sector employment among STEM graduates in the Ghanaian context. Existing work tends to focus on private sector readiness and skill alignment without systematically examining the public sector as a distinct outcome. Second, the alignment between career intentions and realised employment outcomes has received limited attention in the Ghanaian literature, despite its importance for understanding where labour market interventions are most needed. Third, the role of public service motivation so well established in the public administration literature has rarely been tested empirically in the context of technical and STEM-trained graduates in sub-Saharan Africa, where the interaction between intrinsic civic values and structural economic incentives may take distinctive forms.

This study addresses these gaps by examining the determinants of public sector employment among STEM professionals at Ashesi University, Ghana, using a quantitative cross-sectional survey design that integrates demographic, socio-economic, perceptual, motivational, and expectancy-based predictors. The theoretical framework developed above spanning human capital theory, labour market segmentation, matching theory, public

service motivation, and expectancy theory provides the analytical scaffolding for the hypotheses tested.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This study adopted a quantitative research design using a cross-sectional survey approach to examine the determinants of public sector employment among STEM professionals in Ghana. Quantitative research method is suitable for the study as it examines relationship between variables and tested theoretical propositions using statistical methods (Creswell & Creswell, 2017). The cross-sectional design allows data to be collected from respondents at a single point in time, enabling the researcher to analyze patterns of career intentions, employment outcomes, and the factors influencing sectoral employment decisions among STEM students and graduates. Such designs are widely used in labour market and public administration research because they provide a systematic way to quantify perceptions, motivations, and socio-economic characteristics that influence employment behaviour (Bryman, 2016).

The design is also particularly relevant in this research because it allows for testing the extent to which demographic, socio-economic factors, motivations and attitudes toward public service work affect the decision of job selection. Through use of a structured questionnaire and standardized scales, the study produces comparable data that could be statistically tested using descriptive and inferential statistics. In addition, quantitative survey designs have proved valuable for testing theoretical frameworks including motivation to public service, expectancy theory and labour market matching as possible explanations for preferences toward public or private sector work (Perry et al. 2010). In sum, the design is a robust approach toward testing whether or not career intentions will relate to outcomes of employment in both public and private sectors among STEM professionals in Ghana.

3.2 Study Area / Institutional Context

The study was conducted at Ashesi University which is in Berekuso. Ashesi University was established in 2002 and recognized as one of the top private universities in Ghana particularly in regard to the provision of technology-oriented education with a focus on ethics, innovation and interdisciplinary studies. Ashesi University provides a number of science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) courses including computer

science, engineering, management information systems. The Ashesi curriculum uses problem-solving based learning while the development of technological skills and leadership are placed a strong emphasis upon (Ashesi University, 2024).

Choosing Ashesi University for the purpose of this research seems appropriate given the fact that it is becoming a prominent center for the teaching and training of STEM subjects and technologies in Ghana. The universities and colleges, therefore, stand at the forefront of supply of the human resources required for development process and the drive toward digitalization. STEM education is gaining prominence as evidenced in Ghana's national policies such as the Science, Technology and Innovation Policy and wider digital governance reforms in the country that look to developing technological capacity in the private and public spheres National Science, Technology and Innovation Policy 2021. Hence, an institution like Ashesi is the most pertinent place to analyze educational background and labor market expectations in shaping job preferences of STEM graduates.

In addition, the university's diverse student body and strong industry engagement make it a useful setting for studying career decision-making among emerging professionals. Students and recent graduates from Ashesi often transition into careers in technology, entrepreneurship, consulting, and public service, reflecting the broader labour market dynamics facing STEM graduates in Ghana. By focusing on final-year students, masters students and recent graduates from STEM-related programs at Ashesi University, the study captures individuals who are either preparing to enter the labour market or who have recently transitioned into employment, thereby providing insight into both career intentions and realized employment outcomes.

3.3 Target Population

The population targeted for this study are all Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics (STEM) related undergraduate students pursuing studies at Ashesi University, Ghana. Ashesi University has a good variety of undergraduate programs focused on STEM education. These include programs under the umbrella of Computer Science, Engineering and Information Systems. Specifically, some of the popular courses include Computer Science, Management Information Systems, Computer Engineering, Electrical Engineering, Mechanical Engineering, Mechatronic Engineering, and Biological Engineering. The goal of these programs is to equip students with strong technical expertise, problem-solving ability and critical thinking to enable them confront challenges in technology and the society (Ashesi University, 2024). Undergraduate students currently

enrolled in these programs were targeted because the individuals involved are participating in STEM based education and their participation, representations or experience in STEM based domains is what need to be investigated.

The study particularly focuses on students within or have graduated from these STEM programmes because universities globally and in Africa often experience gender disparities in science and engineering disciplines. At Ashesi University, although the institution actively works to promote gender balance and encourage women’s participation in STEM, these fields have historically been male-dominated (Ashesi University, 2024). The target population therefore encompasses all undergraduate and master students at Ashesi University in both sexes enrolled in the aforementioned STEM programs, and also recent graduates who would offer reflective feedback on their educational experience and subsequent lives upon graduation from their respective program. The purpose of this study includes student representatives of the same level and recent graduates of each respective STEM program at Ashesi University to garner more diverse insight into students involved in STEM programs at Ashesi University.

3.4 Sampling Technique

A stratified random sampling technique was used in this research. This sampling method was employed to ensure that all STEM programs in Ashesi University were well-represented in the sample. Stratified random sampling is a sampling method wherein a population is divided into sub-groups called strata based on characteristics they possess and a certain number of individuals is then selected randomly from each stratum in proportion to its size in the population (Creswell & Creswell, 2017). In this research, the strata included Computer Science, Management Information Systems, Computer Engineering, Electrical Engineering, Mechanical Engineering, Mechatronic Engineering and Biological Engineering. This made sure that students from all of these departments were adequately sampled.

3.5 Sample Size Determination

The sample size was determined using Yamane’s (1973) formula for finite populations:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where:

- (*n*) = required sample size,

- (N) = target population size (estimated based on Ashesi's STEM enrollment and recent graduates),
- (e) = margin of error (set at 0.05 for 5% precision).

A 95% confidence level was applied. Given the approximate finite population (considering current enrollment ~1,830 total, with a substantial STEM proportion and recent alumni), the calculation yielded a target sample of 312 respondents. This size is adequate for binary logistic regression, which requires sufficient cases per predictor to avoid overfitting (generally 10–20 events per variable), and for reliable descriptive and inferential statistics in survey research.

3.6 Data Collection Method

Primary data were collected using a structured questionnaire administered electronically via Google Forms. This online platform was chosen for its efficiency in reaching dispersed respondents (current students and recent graduates), cost-effectiveness, automatic data entry to reduce errors, and features for anonymity and consent tracking. The questionnaire link was distributed through official Ashesi channels (e.g., student platforms, alumni networks, and other reachable channels) with follow-up reminders to maximize response rates.

Participants first encountered the consent statement, affirming voluntary participation, confidentiality, academic use only, and the right to withdraw. Responses were collected over a defined period to ensure cross-sectional consistency.

3.7 Research Instrument (Questionnaire Design)

The research instrument is a structured, self-administered questionnaire developed specifically for this study and administered via Google Forms. Given that the instrument was purpose-built rather than adopted from an existing validated tool, a detailed overview of its ten sections is provided here to give the reader a clear picture of the questions asked and the constructs measured; the full questionnaire is reproduced in Appendix A.

The first section obtains informed consent and confirms respondent eligibility through two screening questions that verify STEM field of study and current academic or employment status. Section 2 collects core demographic information including age, gender, and academic field of study, while Section 3 captures socio-economic background through questions on household economic status, the highest educational attainment and occupational sector of the main household breadwinner, scholarship receipt, and the degree

to which family influences career decisions. Together, these three sections provide the demographic and socio-economic control variables used in the regression models.

Sections 4 to 6 represents the perceptual aspect of the instrument. Section 4 uses 5-point Likert-items ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree that captures four dimensions of public sector job perceptions including; salary competitiveness (four items, Q12-Q15), job security (five items, Q16-Q20), career innovation and development opportunities (four items, Q21-Q24), and social status and significance (four items, Q25-Q28). From the 17 Likert-scale items in section 4 the following indices were constructed; Salary Index (SalaryIndex), Job Security Index (JobSecurityIndex), Innovation Index (InnovationIndex) and Prestige Index (PrestigeIndex). Section 5 uses 4 Likert-scale items (Q29-Q32) which is an adapted version of Perry's (1996) PSM scale to gauge the extent to which an individual is internally motivated toward a greater calling such as civil duty, common welfare and civic engagement and from these items the Motivation Index (MotivationIndex) was created. Section 6 used three Likert-scale items (Q33-Q35) which operationalizes Expectancy Theory and measures the extent to which the respondents believe effort put in the public sector will results in meaningful reward and prestige and in turn generates the Expectancy Index (ExpectancyIndex).

Section 7 measures labour market matching perceptions through three items (Q36-Q38) covering perceived skill-job alignment between the respondent's STEM training and available public sector positions, awareness of relevant government vacancies, and perceptions of recruitment transparency, from which the Labour Market Matching Index (LMM_Index) is derived. Section 8 and 9 captures career intentions and actual employment outcomes through a branching structure: students are asked to state their intended sector of employment after graduation and their level of confidence in that intention, while graduates are asked to identify the sector in which they intended to work during their final year of study and their current sector of employment, enabling the study to measure the gap between stated intention and realised outcome. Section 9 collects additional employment-related details from graduates, including industry, position level, average monthly wage, working hours, employer type, enterprise size, and supervisory responsibility. Section 10 presents five Likert items measuring job satisfaction across dimensions of salary adequacy, work-life balance, skills utilisation, advancement opportunities, and overall satisfaction, administered only to currently employed respondents.

3.8 Hypotheses

To empirically examine the determinants of public sector employment among STEM graduates, the study formulates a set of testable hypotheses grounded in the theoretical framework and existing literature. These hypotheses capture the influence of demographic characteristics, motivational factors, and labour market perceptions on individuals' likelihood of choosing public sector employment.

Overall, these hypotheses suggest a general context in which sector choice between STEM graduates is affected by the supply-side of the market and individual preferences on one hand and the demand-side and labour market structure on the other. On the supply side, individual characteristics such as gender and age combine with individual motives, specifically the public service motivation, in determining graduates' appraisal of career choices. It is assumed that these factors encompass variations in values, perceived risks and the stages of one's life that affect the preferences for stability, societal effects and the future long-term secure employment. This view supports the argument on the gendered occupational sorting as well as role expectations, stating that men and women tend to differ in preferences as per gendered socialization (Eagly and Wood, 2012; Dufault et al., 2023). It also is compatible with the theory of life-cycle and career stage, where different ages are expected to possess varying job security preferences and a propensity for stable jobs (Ng et al., 2005; Midttun, 2007). Henceforth, measures like MotivationIndex and JobSecurityIndex can shed light on the psychologised motives that influence occupational choice and, extend the use of demographic determinants in research as suggested in studies related to behaviour and public administration (Perry and Wise, 1990; Vandenabeele, 2007).

At the same time, the framework recognises that employment decisions are not made in isolation from labour market realities. Perceptions of skill alignment and effort-reward structures reflect the demand-side conditions that either facilitate or constrain entry into the public sector. Following Labour Market Segmentation Theory (Doeringer and Piore, 1971), the public sector is a stable place of employment with institutional safeguards and, as such, attracts individuals less risk-averse. Labour Market Matching Theory proposes that individuals accept jobs in which they are most efficient, implying that those who believe they fit best with the technical requirements of a job may enter the public sector more readily (Mortensen and Pissarides, 1994). Moreover, Expectancy Theory suggests that motivation is a function of the association between effort and performance, and performance and reward; individuals will be motivated if they believe that this association

is likely (Vroom, 1964; Ayee, 2008). Given the variations in job conditions and institution quality between labour markets in developing and sub-Saharan African countries, these beliefs are particularly relevant (Dufault et al., 2023). Together these hypotheses combine individual level motivations with the structure of the labour market to derive a thorough theoretical argument to explain empirical results.

H₁ = Female STEM graduates are more likely than male graduates intend or realise public sector employment.

H₂ = Older STEM graduates are more likely to choose or be employed in public sector roles than younger ones.

H₃ = STEM graduates with higher levels of public service motivation are more likely to intend or realise public sector employment.

H₄ = STEM graduates who place a higher value on job security are more likely to choose public sector employment.

H₅ = STEM graduates who perceive stronger alignment between their technical skills and public sector job requirements are more likely to choose public sector employment.

H₆ = STEM graduates who perceive a stronger relationship between effort and reward in the public sector are more likely to choose public sector employment.

3.9 Variables and Measurement

- **Dependent Variables:** binary (Public sector = 1; Non-public sector [private, NGO, self-employed, unemployed, further studies] = 0). For students, this uses intended sector; for graduates, current employment.
- **Independent Variables:**
 - a) Demographic: Age (continuous), gender (categorical), academic field (categorical), GPA (ordinal). Age and gender serve as demographic control variables in all regression model specifications.
 - b) Socio-economic: Household status (ordinal), parental education/occupation (categorical), scholarship (categorical), family influence (ordinal).
 - c) Perception: Composite/individual Likert scores for salary, security, innovation, prestige.

- d) Motivational: Public service motivation (Likert composite).
- e) Expectation: Expectancy items (Likert).
- f) Labour Market: Skill alignment, awareness, transparency (Likert).

All perceptual/motivational items use 5-point scales for ordinal treatment or summation into indices.

3.10 Data Analysis Techniques

The data collected from the questionnaire were analysed using quantitative statistical techniques in order to examine the factors influencing STEM students' and recent graduates' intentions to pursue employment in the public sector. After the data collection process, responses were coded and entered into statistical software for analysis. The analysis began with data cleaning and screening, which involved checking for incomplete responses, inconsistencies, and potential data entry errors. Descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations were then used to summarize the demographic characteristics of respondents, including gender, programme of study, and academic status (student or recent graduate). Descriptive analysis also helped to present general trends regarding respondents' perceptions of public sector employment, such as views on salary competitiveness, job security, career advancement opportunities, and working conditions.

Beyond descriptive and comparative statistics to further explore relationships among study variables, inferential statistical procedures were employed. To test relationship among demographic characteristics and employees' intention to work in the public sector, crosstabulation and chi-square analyses were used. The analysis also uses regression to determine the relationship among variables (perceptions of public sector on salary, job security, opportunity for career development, work environment) and the probability of working in the public sector. The output of this study was represented in tables and statistical summaries.

Model form:

Model Specifications

1. Demographic Factors Model

$$PublicSector_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Male_i + \beta_2 Age_i + \varepsilon_i$$

Description

This baseline model examines the influence of demographic characteristics on public sector choice.

- β_0 : Constant (intercept)
- β_1 : Coefficient for gender
- β_2 : Coefficient of age
- $Male_i$: Gender of respondents (1 = male, 0 = female)
- Age_i : Age of respondent in years (continuous)
- ε_i : Error term

2. Job Preferences Model

$$PublicSector_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Male_i + \beta_2 Age_i + \beta_3 SalaryIndex_i + \beta_4 JobSecurityIndex_i + \varepsilon_i$$

Description

This model focuses on job-related preferences.

- β_0 : Constant (intercept)
- β_1 : Coefficient for gender
- β_2 : Coefficient of age
- β_3 : Coefficient for salary competitiveness perception
- β_4 : Coefficient for job security valuation
- $Male_i$: Gender of respondents (1 = male, 0 = female)
- Age_i : Age of respondent in years (continuous)
- $SalaryIndex_i$: Composite index measuring perceived salary competitiveness of the public sector relative to the private sector (mean of Q12 – Q15)
- $JobSecurityIndex_i$: Composite index measuring the importance placed on employment stability and job security as a career attribute (mean of Q16 – Q20)
- ε_i : Error term

3. Full Model

$$PublicSector_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Male_i + \beta_2 Age_i + \beta_3 SalaryIndex_i + \beta_4 JobSecurityIndex_i + \beta_5 MotivationIndex_i + \beta_6 LLM_Index_i + \varepsilon_i$$

Description

This model integrates demographic, economic, and motivational factors.

- β_0 : Constant (intercept)
- β_1 : Coefficient for gender
- β_2 : Coefficient of age
- β_3 : Coefficient for salary competitiveness perception
- β_4 : Coefficient for job security valuation
- β_5 : Coefficient for public service motivation
- β_6 : Coefficient for labour market matching perception
- $Male_i$: Gender of respondents (1 = male, 0 = female)
- Age_i : Age of respondent in years (continuous)

- *SalaryIndex_i*: Composite index measuring perceived salary competitiveness of the public sector relative to the private sector (mean of Q12 – Q15)
- *JobSecurityIndex_i*: Composite index measuring the importance placed on employment stability and job security as a career attribute (mean of Q16 – Q20)
- *MotivationIndex_i*: Composite index measuring public service motivation – the intrinsic orientation toward civic duty (mean of Q29 – Q32)
- *LLM_Index_i*: Composite index measuring perceived alignment between the respondent's STEM skills and public sector job requirement, and awareness of relevant vacancies (mean of Q36 – Q38)
- ε_i : Error term

4. Extended Model

$$\begin{aligned} \text{PublicSector}_i = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Male}_i + \beta_2 \text{Age}_i + \beta_3 \text{SalaryIndex}_i \\ & + \beta_4 \text{JobSecurityIndex}_i + \beta_5 \text{MotivationIndex}_i + \beta_6 \text{LLM_Index}_i \\ & + \beta_7 \text{InnovationIndex}_i + \beta_8 \text{PrestigeIndex}_i \\ & + \beta_9 \text{ExpectancyIndex}_i + \varepsilon_i \end{aligned}$$

Description

This model expands the framework to include psychological and workplace perception factors.

- β_0 : Constant (intercept)
- β_1 : Coefficient for gender
- β_2 : Coefficient of age
- β_3 : Coefficient for salary competitiveness perception
- β_4 : Coefficient for job security valuation
- β_5 : Coefficient for public service motivation
- β_6 : Coefficient for labour market matching perception
- β_7 : Coefficient for innovation and professional growth perception
- β_8 : Coefficient for occupational prestige perception
- β_9 : Coefficient for effort – reward expectancy perception
- Male_i : Gender of respondents (1 = male, 0 = female)
- Age_i : Age of respondent in years (continuous)
- *SalaryIndex_i*: Composite index measuring perceived salary competitiveness of the public sector relative to the private sector (mean of Q12 – Q15)
- *JobSecurityIndex_i*: Composite index measuring the importance placed on employment stability and job security as a career attribute (mean of Q16 – Q20)
- *MotivationIndex_i*: Composite index measuring public service motivation – the intrinsic orientation toward civic duty (mean of Q29 – Q32)
- *LLM_Index_i*: Composite index measuring perceived alignment between the respondent's STEM skills and public sector job requirement, and awareness of relevant vacancies (mean of Q36 – Q38)
- *InnovationIndex_i*: Composite index measuring perceived opportunities for professional growth, skill development, and innovation within public sector employment (mean of Q21 – Q24)

- *PrestigeIndex_i*: Composite index measuring the perceived social status, recognition, and associated with public sector careers (mean of Q25 – Q28)
- *ExpectancyIndex_i*: Composite index measuring the perceived probability that effort in the public sector will lead to meaningful career recognition and reward, operationalising Vroom's (1961) expectancy – instrument – valence chain (mean of Q33 – Q35)
- ε_i : Error term

5. Employment Outcome Model (Graduates)

$$\begin{aligned} \text{PublicSector}_i = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Male}_i + \beta_2 \text{Age}_i + \beta_3 \text{SalaryIndex}_i \\ & + \beta_4 \text{JobSecurityIndex}_i + \beta_5 \text{MotivationIndex}_i + \beta_6 \text{LLM_Index}_i \\ & + \beta_7 \text{InnovationIndex}_i + \beta_8 \text{PrestigeIndex}_i \\ & + \beta_9 \text{ExpectancyIndex}_i + \varepsilon_i \end{aligned}$$

Description

This model looks at actual employment outcomes rather than intentions.

- β_0 : Constant (intercept)
- β_1 : Coefficient for gender
- β_2 : Coefficient of age
- β_3 : Coefficient for salary competitiveness perception
- β_4 : Coefficient for job security valuation
- β_5 : Coefficient for public service motivation
- β_6 : Coefficient for labour market matching perception
- β_7 : Coefficient for innovation and professional growth perception
- β_8 : Coefficient for occupational prestige perception
- β_9 : Coefficient for effort – reward expectancy perception
- Male_i : Gender of respondents (1 = male, 0 = female)
- Age_i : Age of respondent in years (continuous)
- SalaryIndex_i : Composite index measuring perceived salary competitiveness of the public sector (mean of Q12 – Q15)
- $\text{JobSecurityIndex}_i$: Composite index measuring the value placed on employment stability (mean of Q16 – Q20)
- MotivationIndex_i : Composite index measuring public service motivation (mean of Q29 – Q32)
- LLM_Index_i : Composite index measuring perceived skill – job alignment and vacancy awareness (mean of Q36 – Q38)
- InnovationIndex_i : Composite index measuring perceived innovation and professional growth opportunities in the public sector (mean of Q21 – Q24)
- PrestigeIndex_i : Composite index measuring the perceived social status and impact of public sector careers (mean of Q25 – Q28)
- ExpectancyIndex_i : Composite index measuring the perceived effort – reward linkage in the public sector (mean of Q33 – Q35)
- ε_i : Error term

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section contains and discusses the empirical findings obtained by the analytical framework. The content is organized in order of sections: Section 4.1 introduces the descriptive information of the respondents (312 individuals) about their demographics and academic backgrounds. Section 4.2 presents cross-tabulation and chi-square analyses examining bivariate relationships between sector preference and key demographic variables. Section 4.3 reports the descriptive statistics and mean index scores for the seven composite perception indices. Section 4.4 presents the results of five binary logistic regression models estimated for the student and graduate sub-samples, together with average marginal effects. Section 4.5 interprets the findings against the six research hypotheses. Throughout, the results are situated within the theoretical framework and related to the broader literature on STEM labour markets and public sector employment in Ghana.

4.1 Descriptive Statistics and Sample Characteristics

A total of 312 respondents participated in the study. The sample comprises two analytically distinct sub-groups: 163 students (final-year undergraduate students and Master's students without current employment) and 149 employed graduates (graduates who completed their STEM degree within the past five years and are currently employed). The profile of respondents is presented across four dimensions: gender, age, academic status, and academic field.

4.1.1 Gender Distribution

Of the 312 respondents, 170 (54.49%) identified as male and 142 (45.51%) as female. To contextualise this distribution, it is useful to compare the sample composition against both the general population and the higher education landscape in Ghana. Ghana's 2021 Population and Housing Census reported the population with almost the same share of male (49.3%) and female (50.7%) (Ghana Statistical Service, 2021), and hence, the percentage of male in this sample (54.49%) has not much higher than the percentage share of male population. While looking at tertiary education, the gap of males to females becomes significantly wide: Ghana Tertiary Education Commission shows males comprise 53% of all students enrollments nationally in higher education where women disproportionately study humanities, social sciences and education subjects as opposed to STEM courses (Mohammed et al., 2022). More specifically in STEM, the UNESCO report (2024) places the percentage of female STEM students in higher education to be 35% which shows that

the percentage of women in this study (45.51%) is significantly larger than that in STEM regions. This indicate that the organizational culture and gender policies in Ashesi University might have led to a more gender balanced STEM student population. Despite the lower proportion of female respondents, the sample provides sufficient variation to test gender effects in the regression models. The gender composition is reported in Table 1.

Table 1. Gender Distribution of Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	170	54.49
Female	142	45.51
Total	312	100.0

Source: Author's computation (2026)

4.1.2 Age Distribution

The sample spans a relatively young age range, consistent with the early-career profile of STEM graduates. The mean age across the full sample is 26.78 years ($\sigma = 4.83$), with ages ranging from 19 to 44 years. The largest age group is 20-24 years, comprising 37.94% of respondents, followed by 25-28 years (30.55%), 30-39 years (29.90%), and 40 and above (1.61%). The concentration of respondents in the 20-28 age band reflects the fact that the majority of participants are recent graduates or final-year students, consistent with the study's target population of early-career STEM professionals.

Table 2. Age Distribution of Respondents

Age Group	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Cum. %
20-24	118	37.94	37.94
25-29	95	30.55	68.49
30-39	93	29.90	98.39
40+	5	1.61	100
Total	312	100.0	

Source: Author's computation (2026). Mean age = 26.78 years; $\sigma = 4.83$

4.1.3 Academic Status, Field of Study and Cumulative GPA

In terms of academic status, 41.03% of respondents are final-year undergraduate students, 33.97% are graduates who completed their STEM degree within the last five years, 11.22% are Master's students currently enrolled without employment, and the remaining 13.78% are Master's students who are concurrently employed. By field,

Computer Science is the most common major (31.73%), followed closely by Engineering (31.09%), then Natural Sciences (17.63%), Mathematics (15.38%), and Management Information Systems (4.17%). The proportions by major broadly represent the proportions of majors in the STEM program at Ashesi, which prioritizes engineering and computer science programs.

Looking at the academic achievements, the distribution of the overall GPA points to that most of the respondents are at the medium performance level: 33.97% respondents had a GPA between 2.5 to 2.9, while 28.53% respondents reported a GPA between 3.0 to 3.49. A relatively smaller proportion respondents have GPAs in the lower range: 18.27% respondents had a GPA between 2.0 to 2.49, while only 10.26% respondents achieved GPA of 3.5 and above, 8.97% respondents had GPA less than 2.0. Thus, academic performance of the students are in a relatively uniform level. This may be meaningful in analyzing career choice and employment status differences.

The academic status, field of study and cumulative gpa composition is reported in Table 3, Table 4, Table 5.

Table 3. Academic Status of Respondents

Academic Status	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Final-year undergrad. students	128	41.03
Mater's students (not working)	35	11.22
Graduates (last 5 years)	106	33.97
Master's students (employed)	43	13.78
Total	312	100.0

Source: Author's computation (2026)

Table 4. Field of Study of Respondents

Academic Field	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Computer Science	99	31.73
Engineering	97	31.09
Management Information Systems	13	4.17
Mathematics	48	15.38
Natural Sciences	55	17.63
Total	312	100.0

Source: Author's computation (2026)

Table 5. Cumulative GPA of Respondents

GPA	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Below 2.0	57	18.27
2.0-2.49	106	33.97
2.5-2.9	89	28.53
3.0-3.49	32	10.26
3.5 and above	28	8.97
Total	312	100.0

Source: Author's computation (2026)

4.2 Bivariate Analysis: Cross-tabulations and Chi-Square Tests

Before turning to the regression models, this section examines bivariate associations between sector preference and the key demographic variables using cross-tabulation and Pearson chi-square tests. These analyses serve two purposes: they describe the raw patterns of sector preference across sub-groups, and they provide a preliminary test of whether demographic differences in sector choice are statistically detectable before controlling for other variables.

4.2.1 Sector Intention by Gender

Table 6 presents the cross-tabulation of students' intended sector after graduation by gender. Among female students, 52.0% expressed an intention to work in the public sector, compared to only 32.25% of male students, and showed somewhat higher tendency to private sector employment (28% vs 26.88%). Conversely, male students were more likely to intend NGO or international organisation employment (16.12%) than females (14.66%). A Pearson chi-square test yielded $\chi^2(4) = 14.25$, $p = 0.0065$, indicating a statistically significant association between gender and intended sector of employment at the 1% level. This is a strong early indication that gender plays a meaningful role in shaping public sector career intentions, providing preliminary support for H1.

Table 6. Intended Sector after Graduation by Gender

Gender	NGO/Intl Org. (%)	Private (%)	Public (%)	Self- Employ (%)	Undecided (%)	Total (%)
Female	14.66	28.0	52.0	4.0	1.33	100.0
Male	16.12	26.88	32.25	11.82	12.90	100.0

Source: Author's computation (2026). $\chi^2(4) = 14.25$, $p = 0.0065$

4.2.2 Sector Intention by Age Group

The cross-tabulation of intended sector by age group shows a non-monotonic pattern. Public sector intent among the 20-24 age group is 47.38% and declines in the 25-29 group (25.53%), before rising again among the 30-39 group (47.61%). It can be seen that the eldest group (40+) has the lowest percentage of public sector intention (25.0%), but since it is such a small group (n=5), this statistic should be treated with caution. The chi-square test yields $\chi^2(12) = 19.50$, $p = 0.077$, which falls short of the conventional 5% significance level. The association between age and sector intention is therefore statistically marginal at the bivariate level. This result is not unexpected, as age operates in conjunction with other factors notably socio-economic background and career maturity that are better captured in the multivariate framework. Table 7 presents the cross-tabulation of students' sector intention by age group.

Table 7. Sector Intention by Age Group

Age Group	NGO/Intl Org. (%)	Private (%)	Public (%)	Self- Employ (%)	Undecided (%)	Total (%)
20-24	14.73	20.0	47.36	8.42	9.47	100.0
25-29	19.14	46.80	25.53	6.38	2.12	100.0
30-39	9.52	19.04	47.61	14.28	9.52	100.0
40+	25.0	25.0	25.0	0.0	25.0	100.0

Source: Author's computation (2026). $\chi^2(12) = 19.50$, $p = 0.077$

4.2.3 Sector Intention by GPA

No statistically significant association is found between cumulative GPA and intended sector of employment. The chi-square test yields $\chi^2(16) = 12.23$, $p = 0.727$. Public sector intent varies only modestly across GPA categories, ranging from 35.71% among respondents with GPA below 2.0 to 35.71% among those with GPA of 3.5 and above, and the differences are not systematic. Academic performance as measured by GPA does not appear to independently sort graduates into particular sector intentions, at least at the bivariate level. This result is consistent with the general literature indicating that perceived or motivational rather than achievement characteristics influence choice of sector (Vandenabeele, 2007). Table 8 presents the cross-tabulation of students' sector intention by cumulative GPA.

Table 8. Sector Intention by GPA

GPA	NGO/Intl Org. (%)	Private (%)	Public (%)	Self- Employ (%)	Undecided (%)	Total (%)
2.0-2.49	18.75	34.37	37.5	6.25	3.12	100.0
2.5-2.9	15.25	30.50	42.37	5.08	6.77	100.0
3.0-3.49	16.52	22.44	44.89	8.16	8.16	100.0
3.5 and above	7.14	14.28	35.71	21.42	21.42	100.0
Below 2.0	14.28	28.57	35.71	14.28	14.28	100.0

Source: Author's computation (2026). $\chi^2(16) = 12.23$, $p = 0.727$

4.2.4 Career Intention vs Realised Employment (Graduate Flow Analysis)

A critical question for this study is whether the sector that graduates intended to enter during their final year corresponds to where they actually ended up working. Table 9 presents the intention-to-outcome transition matrix for the graduate sub-sample. Among those who intended public sector employment in their final year, 66.66% are currently employed in the public sector, the highest within-category retention rate across all intended sectors. However, 16.66% of those who intended public sector employment ended up in the private sector, and a further 14.58% in self-employment. Of those that intended private sector work, 48.83% are now working in the private sector while 32.55% are now working in the public sector. These movements between the private and public sectors demonstrate interesting inconsistencies between stated intentions and actual outcome. The overall chi-square test for this association yields $\chi^2(16) = 23.00$, $p = 0.113$, indicating that the relationship between intended and realised sector is not statistically significant at conventional levels, reflecting the considerable degree of post-graduation preference revision and structural re-routing that the data display.

Table 9. Intended Sector (Final Year) vs Current Sector of Employment

Intended Sector	NGO/Intl Org. (%)	Private (%)	Public (%)	Self- Employed (%)	Other (%)
NGO	12.0	28.0	48.0	8.0	4.0
Private sector	9.3	48.83	32.55	6.97	2.32
Public sector	2.08	16.66	66.66	14.58	0.0
Self-employment	4.54	18.18	63.63	9.09	4.5
Undecided	9.09	18.18	63.63	9.09	0.0

Source: Author's computation (2026). $\chi^2(16) = 23.00$, $p = 0.113$

4.3 Descriptive Statistics for Composite Indices

Seven composite perception indices are constructed from the 26-item Likert battery administered in Sections 4 to 6 of the questionnaire, as specified earlier. Prior to standardisation, all indices are scored on a 1-5 scale, where 1 represents Strong Disagreement and 5 represents Strong Agreement with statements describing each dimension of public sector employment. Table 10 and Table 11 presents the descriptive statistics for the seven indices before and after standardisation. To examine how perceptions of public sector employment differ across career pathways, Figure 1 presents a heatmap of mean index scores across all observed sector transition pathways. Each cell in the heatmap represents the mean score on a given index for respondents within a particular sector group, enabling a simultaneous visual comparison of how salary competitiveness, job security, innovation, prestige, motivation, expectancy, and labour market matching perceptions vary across all sector groups and both sub-samples in a single display.

Table 10. Descriptive Statistics for Composite Perception Indices (Pre-standardization, N = 312)

Index	N	mean	SD	Min	Median	Max
SalaryIndex	312	3.17	0.54	1.75	3.25	4.50
JobsecurityIndex	312	3.03	0.47	1.40	3.00	4.60
InnovationIndex	312	3.14	0.53	1.50	3.25	4.50
PrestigeIndex	312	3.13	0.52	1.00	3.25	4.50
MotivationIndex	312	3.44	0.57	2.25	3.50	4.75
ExpectancyIndex	312	2.96	0.62	1.33	3.00	4.66
LLM_Index	312	2.98	0.62	1.33	3.00	4.66

Source: Author's computation (2026). Note: All indices scored on a 1-5 Likert scale. Values are means of constituent items before standardization.

Several observations merit comment. The MotivationIndex records the highest mean (3.44), suggesting that respondents across the sample report relatively high levels of public service motivation. The ExpectancyIndex (2.96) and LMM_Index (2.98) record the lowest means, indicating that respondents, on average, are less convinced that the public sector reliably rewards effort or that their technical skills are well-matched to available government positions. The SalaryIndex (3.17), the InnovationIndex (3.14) and the PrestigeIndex (3.13) are tightly grouped around the midpoint of the scale, where respondents neither strongly reject nor accept that the public sector is competitive with respect to those factors.

Table 11. Descriptive Statistics for Composite Perception Indices (Post-standardization, N = 312)

Index	N	mean	SD	Min	Median	Max
SalaryIndex	312	0.00	1.00	-2.63	0.13	2.43
JobsecurityIndex	312	0.00	1.00	-3.42	-0.07	3.26
InnovationIndex	312	0.00	1.00	-3.10	0.19	2.55
PrestigeIndex	312	0.00	1.00	-4.10	0.21	2.61
MotivationIndex	312	0.00	1.00	-2.06	0.09	2.25
ExpectancyIndex	312	0.00	1.00	-2.60	0.05	2.71
LLM_Index	312	0.00	1.00	-2.65	0.03	2.71

Source: Author’s computation (2026). Note: All indices scored on a 1-5 Likert scale. Values are means of constituent items after standardization.

Several observations emerge from Table 11. As expected from the standardization process, all indices have mean values approximately equal to zero and standard deviations close to one, confirming that the variables have been appropriately normalized for comparative analysis. Despite this, variation across the distributions is evident. The maximum values, ranging from 2.25 (MotivationIndex) to 3.26 (JobSecurityIndex), further demonstrate the presence of variability across respondents.

Figure 1 Heatmap of Mean Composite Index Scores by Sector Transition Pathway

Source: Author’s computation (2026). Note: All indices scored on a 1-5 Likert scale. Values are means of constituent items pre-standardization.

Figure 1 presents mean index scores across all observed sector transition pathways for both students and graduates. Respondents on public sector pathways record consistently higher means on SalaryIndex, InnovationIndex, and PrestigeIndex relative to most other transition groups, with the Public sector → Public sector group recording the highest PrestigeIndex mean in the entire heatmap (4.50), indicating that strong perceptions of occupational prestige and social impact are a defining characteristic of committed public sector graduates. The MotivationIndex, by contrast, is elevated across nearly all transition pathways, including NGO (4.00), private sector (4.00), and self-employment groups, rather than being concentrated among public sector-oriented respondents, a pattern consistent with the negative regression coefficients found for MotivationIndex in the statistical models and supporting the interpretation that civic motivation is broadly distributed across sector preferences rather than specifically directed toward the civil service. The ExpectancyIndex and LMM_Index show the clearest differentiation across groups, with stable public sector transition pathways recording higher means (2.90-3.33) than undecided or unemployment-bound groups (1.67-2.67).

4.4 Binary Logistic Regression Results

This section presents the results of five binary logistic regression models. Models 1 through 4 are estimated on the student sub-sample (n = 163) with PublicSectorIntent as the dependent variable. Model 5 is estimated on the graduate sub-sample (n = 149) with PublicSectorEmployment as the dependent variable. All indices were standardised prior to regression (mean = 0, SD = 1), so coefficients reflect the change in log-odds associated with a one standard deviation increase in each index. Average marginal effects (AMEs) are reported to facilitate substantive interpretation of the probability-scale effects. Table 12 and Table 13 presents the logit regression results and marginal effects for all four student models.

Table 12. Binary Logistic Regression Results – Student Sub-Sample (PublicSectorIntent, N = 163)

Predictor	Model 1 (Demo.)	Model 2 (Pref.)	Model 3 (Full)	Model 4 (Extended)
const	1.503 (0.131)	1.621 (0.110)	1.104 (0.283)	0.505 (0.648)
Age	-0.059 (0.135)	-0.064 (0.108)	-0.045 (0.254)	-0.025 (0.552)
Male (Gender)	-0.782 (0.017)	-0.834 (0.014)	-0.0870 (0.015)	-0.921 (0.016)
SalaryIndex		0.419 (0.010)	0.438 (0.010)	0.256 (0.155)
JobsecurityIndex		0.207 (0.210)	0.258 (0.137)	0.382 (0.052)
MotivationIndex			-0.368 (0.036)	-0.427 (0.024)
LLM_Index			0.598 (0.002)	0.602 (0.003)

InnovationIndex				0.218 (0.241)
PrestigeIndex				0.571 (0.007)
ExpectancyIndex				0.510 (0.013)
N	163	163	163	163
Pseudo R ²	0.037	0.081	0.142	0.223
LLR p-value	0.015	0.001	0.000	0.000

Source: Author's computation (2026). Note: Coefficients are log-odds from the binary logistic regression. LLR p-value are in parentheses.

Table 13. Marginal Effects (AME) – Student Sub-Sample (N = 163)

Predictor	Model 1 (Demo.) - AME	Model 2 (Pref.) - AME	Model 3 (Full) - AME	Model 4 (Ext.) - AME
Age	-0.013 (0.125)	-0.013 (0.097)	-0.009 (0.246)	-0.004 (0.549)
Male (Gender)	-0.180 (0.010)	-0.180 (0.008)	-0.172 (0.009)	-0.161 (0.010)
SalaryIndex		0.090 (0.005)	0.086 (0.005)	0.045 (0.145)
JobsecurityIndex		0.044 (0.201)	0.051 (0.128)	0.067 (0.042)
MotivationIndex			-0.073 (0.027)	-0.075 (0.016)
LLM_Index			0.118 (0.000)	0.105 (0.001)
InnovationIndex				0.038 (0.234)
PrestigeIndex				0.100 (0.003)
ExpectancyIndex				0.089 (0.008)
N	163	163	163	163
Pseudo R ²	0.037	0.081	0.142	0.223
LLR p-value	0.015	0.001	0.000	0.000

Source: Author's computation (2026). Note: AME = Average Marginal Effect. LLR p-value are in parentheses.

4.4.1 Model 1 - Demographic Factors Model

Model 1 regresses public sector career intention on age and gender only (n = 163). The Pseudo R² is 0.037 and the LLR p-value is 0.015, indicating that the model as a whole is statistically significant at the 5% level. Age exerts a negative and marginally significant effect (coef = -0.059, p = 0.136), suggesting that older students are slightly less likely to express public sector intent in the demographic-only specification, a finding that stands in contrast to H2 and may reflect a cohort or selection effect specific to this sample, in which older final-year students may have already formed stronger private sector networks. The average marginal effect confirms that, holding age constant, male students are 18.0 percentage points less likely than female students to intend public sector employment (AME = -0.180, p = 0.010). This is one of the strongest and most precisely estimated effects in the entire analysis.

4.4.2 Model 2 – Job Preference Model

Model 2 adds SalaryIndex and JobSecurityIndex to the demographic predictors (n = 163). The model improves on Model 1: Pseudo R² rises to 0.081 and the LLR p-value is 0.001. Both gender and salary competitiveness perception emerge as significant predictors. The coefficient on Gender_binary (Male = 1) remains negative and significant (coef = -0.834, p = 0.014; AME = -0.180, p = 0.008), confirming that the gender effect is robust to the inclusion of job preference perceptions. Importantly, SalaryIndex is positively and significantly associated with public sector intent (coef = +0.419, p = 0.010; AME = +0.090, p = 0.005). Students who perceive the public sector as offering more competitive salaries are approximately 9 percentage points more likely to intend public sector employment, a practically meaningful effect. The JobSecurityIndex is positive (coef = +0.207, p = 0.210) but does not reach significance in this specification, suggesting that job security considerations do not play a decisive role in shaping public sector career intentions at this stage. Alternatively, the effects related to salary perceptions are stronger in the short-term. This effect is again possibly related to an age effect, as the sample is primarily composed of young people who are more likely to see high wages as a better indicator of the quality of a career, and more risk-prone in their labor market behavior. Consequently, stability-related factors such as job security may become more relevant at later stages of the career lifecycle rather than during initial career decision-making. Age approaches marginal significance (coef = -0.064, p = 0.108).

4.4.3 Model 3 – Full Model

Model 3 introduces MotivationIndex and LMM_Index alongside all predictors from Models 1 and 2 (n = 163). The model achieves strong statistical significance: Pseudo R² = 0.142, LLR p-value < 2.113e-05. Four of the six predictors are statistically significant. Gender_binary remains negative and highly significant (coef = -0.870, p = 0.015; AME = -0.172, p = 0.009), with male students approximately 17.2 percentage points less likely than female students to intend public sector employment. SalaryIndex remains positive and significant (coef = +0.438, p = 0.010; AME = +0.086, p = 0.005). MotivationIndex is negative and statistically significant (coef = -0.368, p = 0.036; AME = -0.073, p = 0.027), a finding that is counter-intuitive with respect to H3 and is discussed in detail in Section 4.6. LMM_Index is positive and highly significant (coef = +0.598, p = 0.002; AME = +0.118, p = 0.000): students who perceive stronger alignment between their STEM skills and public sector job requirements are approximately 11.8 percentage points more likely to

intend public sector employment, providing strong support for H5. JobSecurityIndex ($p = 0.137$) and Age ($p = 0.254$) remain non-significant in this specification.

4.4.4 Model 4 – Extended Model

Model 4 extends the core model by adding InnovationIndex, PrestigeIndex, and ExpectancyIndex ($n = 163$). The Pseudo R^2 increases to 0.223 and the LLR p -value is $< 1.424e-07$, confirming that the additional perception dimensions contribute meaningfully to explanatory power. Six of the nine predictors are statistically significant. Gender_binary remains significant (coef = -0.921 , $p = 0.016$; AME = -0.161 , $p = 0.010$). MotivationIndex remains negative and significant (coef = -0.427 , $p = 0.024$; AME = -0.075 , $p = 0.016$). LMM_Index remains positive and highly significant (coef = $+0.602$, $p = 0.003$; AME = $+0.105$, $p = 0.001$). JobSecurityIndex reaches significance (coef = $+0.382$, $p = 0.052$; AME = $+0.067$, $p = 0.042$), which offers support to H4 with the extended specification. PrestigeIndex comes positive and significant (coef = $+0.517$, $p = 0.007$; AME = $+0.100$, $p = 0.003$). So students who perceive that public sector work contributes to high social status and impact are about 10.0 percentage points higher on likelihood of public sector career aspiration. ExpectancyIndex is positive and significant (coef = $+0.510$, $p = 0.013$; AME = $+0.089$, $p = 0.008$), directly supporting H6: students who believe their effort will be meaningfully rewarded in the public sector are approximately 9.0 percentage points more likely to intend public sector employment. InnovationIndex ($p = 0.241$) and Age ($p = 0.552$) do not reach significance.

4.4.5 Model 5 – Graduate Employment Model

Model 5 is estimated on the graduate sub-sample ($n = 149$), regressing actual public sector employment on the full set of nine predictors used in Model 4. This model shifts from stated career intention to realised employment outcome, enabling direct comparison of the determinants across the two stages of the career lifecycle. The model Pseudo R^2 is 0.072 and the LLR p -value is 0.091, indicating that the model does not achieve conventional statistical significance at the 5% level. This finding is substantively important in its own right: it suggests that the perceptual and attitudinal variables measured in the survey explain student intentions considerably better than they explain where graduates actually end up working, pointing to the role of structural factors, institutional placement mechanisms (such as Ghana's National Service Scheme), and labour market conditions at the time of graduation that lie outside the model.

At the individual coefficient level, Gender_binary now reverses sign: being male is positively associated with actual public sector employment (coef = +0.606, p = 0.092; AME = +0.136, p = 0.080), approaching significance at the 10% level. This direction reversal from the student models, where male students were significantly less likely to intend public sector employment, is one of the most substantively important findings of the study and is discussed extensively in Section 4.6. MotivationIndex remains negative and statistically significant (coef = -0.467, p = 0.017; AME = -0.105, p = 0.009), providing the most robust single-predictor finding across all five models: across both student intentions and graduate employment, higher public service motivation scores are associated with lower probability of a public sector outcome. SalaryIndex is negative and approaches significance (coef = -0.368, p = 0.070; AME = -0.083, p = 0.058). PrestigeIndex is positive and marginally significant (coef = +0.344, p = 0.103; AME = +0.077, p = 0.092). JobSecurityIndex, LMM_Index, InnovationIndex, ExpectancyIndex, and Age are not significant.

Table 14. Binary Logistic Regression Results – Graduates Sub-Sample (PublicSectorEmployment, N = 149) with Average Marginal Effects

Predictor	Coef. (p-value)	AME (p-value)
const	0.011 (0.993)	-
Age	-0.006 (0.889)	-0.001 (0.888)
Male (Gender)	0.606 (0.092)	0.136 (0.080)
SalaryIndex	-0.368 (0.070)	-0.083 (0.058)
JobsecurityIndex	0.083 (0.655)	0.018 (0.653)
MotivationIndex	-0.467 (0.017)	-0.105 (0.009)
LLM_Index	-0.0539 (0.765)	-0.012 (0.765)
InnovationIndex	0.073 (0.725)	0.016 (0.725)
PrestigeIndex	0.344 (0.103)	0.077 (0.092)
ExpectancyIndex	0.023 (0.899)	0.005 (0.899)
N	149	
Pseudo R ²	0.072	
LLR p-value	0.091	

Source: Author's computation (2026). Note: LLR p-value are in parentheses. AME = Average Marginal Effect

4.5 Hypothesis Testing and Discussion

This section interprets the regression results against each of the six research hypotheses. For each hypothesis, the decision to accept or reject is stated, followed by a discussion of the finding in relation to the theoretical framework and existing empirical evidence.

4.5.1 H1 – Gender and Public Sector Intent (Supported)

H1 predicted that female STEM graduates are more likely than male graduates to intend or realise public sector employment. This hypothesis is strongly supported in the student models. Across all four specifications (Models 1-4), the Gender_binary coefficient is consistently negative, statistically significant, and stable in magnitude. In the extended model, male students are 16.1 percentage points less likely than female students to intend public sector employment (AME = -0.161, $p = 0.010$), holding all other variables constant. This result is consistent with evidence from Eagly and Wood (2012) on gendered occupational socialisation, and with Dufault et al. (2023), who find that women score higher on social responsibility orientations correlated with public service career preferences.

The graduate model (Model 5), however, reveals an important reversal: Gender_binary becomes positive among graduates (AME = +0.136, $p = 0.080$), approaching significance. This reversal suggests that while female students are more likely to intend public sector careers, male graduates are more likely to actually end up there, a discordance that points to structural mechanisms at the transition stage. Plausible explanations for this reversal warrant closer examination. First, post-graduation preference revision may operate differently by gender: female graduates who initially intend public sector employment may revise their preferences after encountering slow and opaque civil service recruitment processes, while male graduates who initially preferred the private sector may more readily accept public sector placements when private sector opportunities do not materialise.

Second, gendered social capital and network effects may disadvantage female graduates at the point of actual sector entry, as informal referral networks through which many government positions are filled tend to be male-dominated in sub-Saharan African labour markets, giving male graduates a structural advantage in accessing public sector vacancies regardless of their stated preferences (Lin, 1999). Third, the National Service Scheme may disproportionately channel male STEM graduates into technical roles within government ministries and agencies, either through gendered assignment practices or because male graduates are more likely to be posted to ICT and engineering units that constitute the bulk of STEM-relevant public sector placements. If this channelling effect is operating, it would produce exactly the pattern observed, higher public sector employment among male graduates not because they prefer it, but because the institutional structure routes them there at higher rates than their pre-graduation preferences would predict. This

intent-to-outcome gender gap implies that efforts to increase female representation in Ghana's public sector STEM workforce must address not only pre-graduation career intention, where female students are already strongly oriented toward government employment, but also the structural mechanisms operating after graduation that prevent those intentions from converting into actual employment outcomes.

4.5.2 H2 – Age and Public Sector Preference (Not Supported)

H2 predicted that older graduates would be more likely to choose public sector employment. This hypothesis is not supported. Across all models, the age coefficient is statistically insignificant, and its sign is negative rather than the hypothesised positive direction. In the extended student model, the AME for age is -0.004 ($p = 0.549$), and in the graduate model, it is -0.001 ($p = 0.888$). The bivariate chi-square test also yielded only marginal significance ($p = 0.077$). The lack of an age effect could be due to the restricted range of ages in the sample, since most respondents are within the 20–29 age bracket. A limited age range can reduce the statistical power of research to pick up age-related effects which might only be significant with a wider career length (Ng et al., 2005). The finding does not invalidate the proposed mechanism but implies that in the relevant range the greater stability of the public sector is not yet strong enough to create significant preferences between sectors.

4.5.3 H3 – Public Service Motivation (Rejected – Negative Effect Found)

H3 predicted that higher public service motivation would increase the likelihood of public sector employment. This hypothesis is rejected. Across all models and both sub-samples, the MotivationIndex coefficient is consistently negative and, in the full, extended, and graduate models, statistically significant. In the extended student model, a one-standard-deviation increase in MotivationIndex is associated with a 7.5 percentage-point reduction in the probability of public sector intent (AME = -0.075 , $p = 0.016$). In the graduate model, the effect is even larger (AME = -0.105 , $p = 0.009$).

This finding is the most theoretically challenging result of the study and warrants careful interpretation. Two explanations are most plausible. First, the PSM scale used in this study adapted from Perry's (1996) general civic motivation instrument may be capturing a broad altruistic orientation that is not specific to government employment. Graduates with high civic motivation may be directing that motivation toward NGOs, international development organisations, or social enterprises, which the data show absorb a meaningful proportion of high-motivation respondents. This interpretation is consistent

with Vandenberg's (2007) observation that PSM does not automatically translate into government employment when alternative prosocial career outlets are available. Second, the finding may reflect a perception gap: highly motivated graduates who are aware of the constraints and bureaucratic limitations of Ghana's civil service may consciously seek to pursue social impact through non-governmental channels. Future research using a sector-specific PSM instrument would help to disambiguate these interpretations.

4.5.4 H4 – Job Security Valuation (Partially Supported)

H4 predicted that students who place a higher value on job security would be more likely to choose public sector employment. This hypothesis receives partial support. The JobSecurityIndex coefficient is consistently positive across the student models, and achieves statistical significance in the extended model (Model 4: AME = +0.067, $p = 0.042$). The effect is not significant in the more parsimonious Models 2 and 3, and turns non-significant in the graduate model (AME = +0.018, $p = 0.653$). The finding in Model 4 supports the prediction of Labour Market Segmentation Theory (Doeringer and Piore, 1971) that the public sector's primary labour market attributes, including employment security, structured career progression, and protection from arbitrary dismissal constitute an independent attractor for risk-averse graduates when controlling for the full set of perceptual dimensions. The non-significance in the graduate model suggests that the job security motive is more salient at the intention-formation stage than at the point of actual sector entry.

4.5.5 H5 – Labour Market Skill-Job Alignment (Strongly Supported)

H5 predicted that graduates who perceive stronger alignment between their STEM skills and public sector requirements would be more likely to choose public sector employment. This hypothesis is strongly supported and represents one of the most consistent findings of the study. In Model 3 (Full Model), LMM_Index achieves high significance (AME = +0.118, $p = 0.000$), and remains significant across all student model specifications including the extended model (AME = +0.105, $p = 0.001$). In the graduate model, the LMM_Index coefficient turns non-significant ($p = 0.765$), again suggesting that the pathway from perceived skill alignment to public sector placement operates more strongly at the intention stage than the realisation stage.

The consistency of the LMM_Index effect across Models 3 and 4 provides the most robust predictive result for the student sub-sample, with a magnitude exceeding that of all other significant predictors. This finding directly validates Labour Market Matching

Theory (Mortensen and Pissarides, 1994) in the Ghanaian STEM context and has clear policy implications: improving STEM graduates' awareness of technical roles available within government, and actively communicating the alignment between STEM competencies and public sector job requirements, could substantially increase the proportion of STEM students who intend to enter the civil service.

4.5.6 H6 – Expectancy-Reward Perception (Supported)

H6 predicted that graduates who perceive a stronger effort-reward linkage in the public sector would be more likely to choose public sector employment. This hypothesis is supported in the extended student model, where ExpectancyIndex is positive and statistically significant (AME = +0.089, $p = 0.008$). The effect size is comparable to that of PrestigeIndex and is consistent with the expectancy-instrumentality-valence framework of Vroom (1964): students who believe that working hard and performing well in the public sector will lead to meaningful career recognition and advancement are approximately 8.0 percentage points more likely to intend a public sector career. The effect does not replicate significantly in the graduate model (AME = +0.005, $p = 0.899$), suggesting that expectancy perceptions formed during study are a stronger predictor of intention than of where graduates ultimately end up, further evidence that structural factors dominate the intention-to-employment transition.

5 DISCUSSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The empirical findings of this study carry meaningful implications for public workforce planning, recruitment policy, institutional design, and university education in Ghana. This chapter translates the regression results and hypothesis outcomes into concrete, evidence-grounded recommendations directed at three principal audiences: government ministries and the Public Services Commission responsible for civil service recruitment; policymakers responsible for STEM education and national labour market strategy; and university administrators and career development offices whose decisions shape how graduates form and act on career intentions. The recommendations are organised around the four most robust empirical findings: the gender gap in public sector intent; the non-significance of age; the unexpected negative effect of public service motivation; the strong positive effects of labour market matching, occupational prestige, and expectancy perceptions.

5.1 Reforming Recruitment to Attract Female STEM Graduates

The intent-to-outcome gap for female STEM graduates points to structural barriers operating at the transition stage, and addressing it carries concrete benefits for both individual graduates and Ghana's public sector more broadly. The motivation for targeted recruitment is therefore not simply equity for its own sake, but a convergence of individual and national developmental interests. At individual level, female STEM graduates in Ghana experience above-average post-graduation unemployment and under-employment compared to their male graduates, this phenomenon is not unique to Ghana but is observed within the sub-Saharan African graduate labour markets (Iwara, 2025), so it is easy to see that helping them into a stable job in the public sector with a predictable career structure is the most direct way of resolving female graduate unemployment and their associated costs.

At the sectoral level, Ghana's public sector is one of the more formalised and consistently remunerated employment environments available to recent graduates, and increasing female representation within it would contribute to narrowing the gender wage gap by channelling more women into roles with standardised, transparent salary scales that are less susceptible to the informal negotiation dynamics that tend to disadvantage women in private sector compensation (Bender, 2003). At the national level, Ghana's digital transformation agenda depends on expanding the technical capacity of government institutions, and given that female STEM students in this study already demonstrate stronger public sector orientation than their male counterparts, they represent an underutilised talent pool whose integration into the civil service would directly serve the state's human capital needs. The Public Services Commission and relevant ministries should therefore pursue targeted recruitment initiatives that reach female STEM graduates through university alumni networks, STEM-focused career fairs, and gender-responsive employer branding that communicates the public sector's family-friendly policies, flexible working arrangements, and institutional protections. Zolak et al. (2025) show that gender-specific, open and merit-based recruitment mechanisms have been shown to be especially conducive to the absorption of women into public service positions. On the other hand, CCS Global Tech (2025) highlight the fact that proactive employer branding toward under-represented groups can have a significant impact on the attraction of technical graduates towards different sectors. Both strategies would help to decrease the number of female graduates remaining unemployed while enhancing public sector technical expertise and fostering a better allocation of jobs that provide stable, high-paying working opportunities justifying the policy investment from social as well as development perspectives.

5.2 Strengthening Labour Market Matching and Skill Alignment Communication

Ghana's government, through the National Information Technology Agency (NITA), the Ministry of Communications and Digitalisation, and the Public Services Commission, should invest in a sustained communication campaign specifically targeted at STEM students and recent graduates that maps current and projected government vacancies onto specific STEM competencies. Role profiles for public sector technical positions should be redesigned in plain, competency-based language that makes visible the connection between a data analytics degree or an engineering qualification and concrete government responsibilities. Internship and attachment programs at ministries, agencies, and state-owned enterprises for STEM students during their penultimate year of university will provide first hand assessment of how well student skills match public sector positions thereby allowing them to form valid impressions during school instead of based on borrowed ideas (Winful, 2003, Brown and Lent, 2019). McGuinness (2006) illustrates how this exposure directly lowers skill mismatch perceptions and increase job matching efficiency, and this could clearly translate to public sector skills pipeline in Ghana.

5.3 Building Occupational Prestige and Strengthening Effort-Reward Credibility

The findings from both sub-samples suggest that the public sector's recruitment challenge among STEM graduates is not solely a compensation problem, but equally a perception and branding problem. Even where salaries cannot immediately match private sector levels, government institutions can substantially improve their attractiveness by communicating the social impact, mission significance, and career development opportunities that public sector employment offers and by demonstrating that performance is genuinely recognised and rewarded within the civil service. The Government of Ghana, through the Office of the Head of Civil Service and the Public Services Commission, should invest in an employer branding strategy that profiles the work of STEM professionals currently employed within government, highlights the national impact of technical roles in digital governance and infrastructure, and communicates clear, transparent pathways for career advancement based on merit. Ayee (2008) identifies weak performance management systems as a principal source of low expectancy perceptions in African civil services; structural reform of performance appraisal and merit-based promotion systems within Ghana's ministries would therefore directly address the expectancy gap identified in this study and increase the public sector's competitiveness for STEM talent. The OECD (2023)

similarly recommends that public employers introduce performance-linked elements into compensation structures for hard-to-fill technical roles as a means of improving both prestige perceptions and expectancy beliefs among prospective applicants.

5.4 Reinterpreting Public Service Motivation

Rather than high public service motivation predicting public sector careers, as Perry and Wise (1990) and Vandenabeele (2007) anticipate, the data show the opposite: STEM graduates with the strongest civic values and prosocial orientations are less likely to choose or end up in government employment. The heatmap of sector transition flows further supports this interpretation, showing that the highest MotivationIndex means are found among NGO/international bound, unemployed, and self-employed respondents, not among those intending or realising public sector careers.

The most plausible interpretation of this finding, consistent with Vandenabeele's (2007) observation that PSM does not automatically translate into government employment when alternative prosocial outlets are available, is that highly motivated STEM graduates are directing their civic values toward non-governmental channels, international development organisations, civil society, and social entrepreneurship that they perceive as offering greater scope for meaningful impact than the bureaucratic constraints of the civil service. This has two distinct sets of implications. First, for the Government of Ghana, the finding signals an urgent need to position the public sector as a genuine site of professional and civic impact, not merely a stable employer. If the most motivated STEM graduates are avoiding the civil service because they perceive it as insufficiently responsive to their civic values, then the recruitment challenge is fundamentally about institutional culture and mission communication, not just compensation. Ministries should articulate clear, compelling narratives about the national development impact of technical roles within government from digitising public health records to building cybersecurity infrastructure that make the connection between civic motivation and civil service work visible and credible to prospective applicants. Second, for researchers and future studies, the finding points to a measurement gap: the PSM instrument used in this study, adapted from Perry's (1996) general civic motivation scale, captures a broad altruistic orientation rather than a specifically government-directed one. Future research in the Ghanaian and broader sub-Saharan African context should develop and validate a sector-specific PSM instrument that distinguishes between motivation directed toward government employment specifically

and motivation directed toward prosocial activity more broadly, in order to generate more precise and actionable predictions.

5.5 Closing the Intention-to-Employment Gap through Institutional Recognition

The intent-to-outcome analysis shows that only 66.66% of graduates who intended public sector employment are currently working there, while 32.55% of those who intended private sector careers have ended up in the public sector. This bidirectional flow indicates that the transition from education to employment is characterised by considerable structural rerouting that is not well explained by the perceptual variables in the model. These patterns carry important implications for institutional design. For the National Service Scheme, which appears to be channelling graduates into the public sector at rates exceeding expressed preferences, the evidence suggests an opportunity: the scheme could be redesigned to function not merely as a short-term placement mechanism, but as a deliberate talent pipeline through which high-performing STEM graduates are identified, mentored, and offered structured pathways into permanent public sector roles. Converting National Service placements into competitive civil service entry points, with clear merit-based criteria and transparent promotion pathways would capitalise on the structural absorption already occurring while building long-term STEM capacity within government. For universities and career development offices, the high number of graduates that have shifted career sector preference before and after graduation in both directions indicates the need for continuous career counseling on expectations regarding the different sectors prior to students' graduation. This would decrease unplanned career transitions in private and public sectors after graduation and increase alignment between investment in human capital and labor outcomes (Siivonen et al., 2023; Lent et al., 1994).

6 CONCLUSION

This study set out to examine the determinants of public sector employment among STEM professionals in Ghana, using a sample of 312 students and graduates from Ashesi University. Drawing on five theoretical frameworks, Human Capital Theory, Labour Market Segmentation Theory, Labour Market Matching Theory, Public Service Motivation Theory, and Expectancy Theory, and estimating five binary logistic regression models across student and graduate sub-samples, the study produced several empirically meaningful findings. Gender emerged as a significant predictor of public sector career intention, with female students substantially more likely to intend government employment

across all model specifications, while the graduate employment model revealed a directional reversal in which male graduates are more likely to actually be working in the public sector, a structural intent-to-outcome gap that points to recruitment mechanisms and post-graduation preference revision as important forces shaping where graduates eventually end up. Perceived skill-job alignment was the strongest individual predictor of public sector intent among students, with a one-standard-deviation increase in LMM_Index associated with an 11.8 percentage point increase in public sector intention, directly validating the Labour Market Matching Theory framework in the Ghanaian STEM context. Occupational prestige and effort-reward expectancy perceptions were also significant positive predictors in the extended model, underscoring that the public sector's recruitment challenge is as much a matter of institutional culture and employer branding as it is of compensation. Most unexpectedly, public service motivation was consistently and significantly negatively associated with public sector outcomes across all model specifications, including the graduate employment model, suggesting that highly motivated graduates are directing their civic values toward NGOs, international organisations, and social enterprises rather than the civil service, a finding that challenges prevailing assumptions in the public administration literature and points to a fundamental mismatch between what Ghana's civil service currently offers and what its most civically motivated STEM graduates are seeking.

Taken together, these findings reveal that the underrepresentation of STEM graduates in Ghana's public sector reflects a complex interaction of structural recruitment barriers, weak skill-alignment communication, low expectancy perceptions, and an institutional culture that fails to capture the civic motivation of the graduates most disposed toward public service. The intention-to-outcome analysis further shows that career preferences are not stable between the point of graduation and actual employment, with meaningful cross-sectoral flows in both directions indicating that structural and institutional forces rather than individual preferences alone play a decisive role in determining where STEM graduates ultimately work. As Ghana advances its digital transformation agenda through the Digital Acceleration Project and the National Science, Technology and Innovation Policy, the capacity of public institutions to attract and retain technically skilled professionals will be critical to whether these ambitions translate into sustained governance improvement. The evidence presented in this study provides an empirical foundation for that effort, identifying where the barriers lie, which graduates are most likely to be reached through targeted intervention, and what recruitment, institutional, and educational reforms

are most likely to close the gap between the STEM talent Ghana is producing and the technical capacity its public sector urgently needs.

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APENDICES

Determinants of Public Sector Employment Among STEM Professionals: Evidence from Ghana

Brilliant Amoah Kwakye | Higher School of Economics | March 2026

Appendix A	Survey Instrument - Full Questionnaire
Appendix B	Regression Outputs - Full Logistic Regression Results and Marginal Effects

Appendix A: Survey Instrument

The following is the complete survey questionnaire administered via Google Forms to 312 respondents comprising final-year STEM students and recent STEM graduates from Ashesi University, Berekuso, Ghana. The instrument is organised into ten sections and was designed specifically for this study.

Section 1: Introduction & Consent

Title:

Determinants of Public Sector Employment Among STEM Professionals in Ghana

Consent Statement (Required – Yes/No)

This survey is a part of a Master’s research study. Your participation is voluntary. All responses will remain confidential and used strictly for academic purposes. You may withdraw at any time.

- I agree to participate
- I do not agree (End survey)

Section 2: Screening Questions

1. Are you currently:
 - Final-year undergraduate student
 - Master’s student
 - Graduate (completed within last 5 years)
 - Other (End survey)
2. Is/Was your field of study in STEM?
(Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics or related fields)
 - Yes
 - No (End survey)

Section 3: Demographic Characteristics

Q#	Question	Response Format
Q3	Age?	Open (years)
Q4	Gender?	Male / Female / Prefer not to say / Other
Q5	Academic field?	Categorical
Q6	Cumulative GPA?	Below 2.0 / 2.0–2.49 / 2.5–2.9 / 3.0–3.49 / 3.5+

Academic field options: Computer Science; Engineering; Mathematics; Natural Sciences; Other.

Section 4: Socio-Economic Background

Q#	Question	Response Format
Q7	To which of the following groups would you assign your household based on your family's ability to afford goods and living expenses (excluding credit or loans)?	8-point ordinal scale
Q8	What is the highest level of education completed by your main breadwinner?	Categorical
Q9	Parental Occupation (Main Breadwinner)?	Public / Private / Self-employed / Unemployed / Other
Q10	Did you receive any scholarship during your studies?	Yes (Full) / Yes (Partial) / No
Q11	Does your family influence your career decisions?	Strongly / Moderately / Slightly / Not at all

Sections 5-8: Perception, Motivation, Expectancy, and Labour Market Indices

Respondents rated all items on a 5-point Likert scale: 1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree.

Q#	Statement	1	2	3	4	5
Section 5A - Salary Competitiveness (Q12-Q15) → SalaryIndex						
Q12	Public sector salaries are more competitive compared to the private sector.	1	2	3	4	5
Q13	Private sector jobs offer higher earning potential over time.	1	2	3	4	5
Q14	Public sector employment provides adequate long-term financial security.	1	2	3	4	5

Q15	Salary growth is faster in the private sector than in the public sector.	1	2	3	4	5
Section 5B - Job Security (Q16-Q20) → JobSecurityIndex						
Q16	Public sector jobs offer higher job security than private sector jobs.	1	2	3	4	5
Q17	Private sector jobs offer better long-term stability than public sector jobs.	1	2	3	4	5
Q18	Job stability is more important to me than high salary.	1	2	3	4	5
Q19	Job security is not a major factor in my career choice.	1	2	3	4	5
Q20	I would accept lower pay in exchange for greater job security.	1	2	3	4	5
Section 5C - Innovation and Professional Growth (Q21-Q24) → InnovationIndex						
Q21	The public sector offers opportunities for innovation.	1	2	3	4	5
Q22	The private sector provides better professional development opportunities.	1	2	3	4	5
Q23	My STEM skills can be effectively utilized in the public sector.	1	2	3	4	5
Q24	Career advancement is clearer in the private sector than in the public sector.	1	2	3	4	5
Section 5D - Prestige and Social Impact (Q25-Q28) → PrestigeIndex						
Q25	Public sector employment is socially prestigious.	1	2	3	4	5
Q26	Private sector careers are more respected in Ghanaian society.	1	2	3	4	5
Q27	Working in the public sector allows me to contribute to national development.	1	2	3	4	5
Q28	The private sector allows greater contribution to national development than the public sector.	1	2	3	4	5
Section 6 - Public Service Motivation (Q29-Q32) → MotivationIndex						
Q29	I am motivated by serving the public interest.	1	2	3	4	5
Q30	I feel a sense of responsibility toward contributing to Ghana's development.	1	2	3	4	5
Q31	I would accept lower pay if the job contributes to societal welfare.	1	2	3	4	5
Q32	I prefer work that benefits society rather than only generating profit.	1	2	3	4	5
Section 7 - Expectancy and Effort-Reward (Q33-Q35) → ExpectancyIndex						
Q33	I believe I have a high chance of succeeding in the public sector recruitment process.	1	2	3	4	5
Q34	If I work in the public sector, I expect my efforts to be recognized.	1	2	3	4	5
Q35	Performance in the public sector is fairly rewarded.	1	2	3	4	5
Section 8 - Labour Market Matching (Q36-Q38) → LMM_Index						
Q36	My academic training aligns with skills required in the public sector.	1	2	3	4	5
Q37	I am aware of public sector job opportunities relevant to my field.	1	2	3	4	5
Q38	The recruitment process in the public sector is transparent.	1	2	3	4	5

Section 9: Career Intentions (Students Only)

Q#	Question	Response Format
Q39	Which sector do you intend to work in after graduation?	Public sector / Private sector / NGO or International Organisation / Self-employment / Undecided
Q40	How confident are you in this career intention?	Not Confident → Very Confident (5-point)

Section 10: Employment Outcomes (Graduates Only)

Q#	Question	Response Format
Q41	During your final year, which sector did you intend to work in?	Public / Private / NGO / Self-employment / Undecided
Q42	What is your current sector of employment?	Public sector / Private sector / NGO / Self-employed / Unemployed
Q43	In which industry do you work?	Categorical (multiple sectors listed)
Q44	What best describe your current position level?	Managers / Professionals / Technicians / Clerical / Service workers / Skilled technical/ Other
Q45	What is your average monthly wage (before tax)?	Below GHS 2,000 / GHS 2,000–5,999 / Above GHS 6,000 / Prefer not to say
Q46	How many hours do you work in a month?	Less than 160 / 160–200 / More than 200
Q47	Is your employer?	Domestic company / Foreign-owned / State-owned enterprise / Government ministry or agency
Q48	Enterprise size?	1–9 / 10–49 / 50–249 / 250+
Q49	Do you supervise other employees?	Yes / No

Section 11: Job Satisfaction (Currently Employed Respondents Only)

Q#	Statement	1	2	3	4	5
Q50	I am satisfied with my current salary.	1	2	3	4	5
Q51	I am satisfied with my work-life balance.	1	2	3	4	5

Q52	I feel secure in my current job.	1	2	3	4	5
Q53	My job utilizes my STEM skills effectively.	1	2	3	4	5
Q54	I am satisfied with promotion opportunities.	1	2	3	4	5

Note: Section 11 (Q50-Q54) was administered only to respondents who indicated current employment. Ratings: 1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree. Source: Author-developed instrument (2026).

Appendix B: Regression Outputs

This appendix presents the complete binary logistic regression outputs referenced in the results and discussions section. Tables B.1 through B.5 report the regression results for each of the five models. Table B.6 - B.9 reports the average marginal effects (AMEs) for the student sub-sample. Table B.10 presents the AMEs for the graduate sub-sample.

Table B.1: Model 1 - Demographic Factors Model (Students, n = 163)

Logit Regression Results						
Dep. Variable:	PublicSectorIntent	No. Observations:	163			
Model:	Logit	Df Residuals:	160			
Method:	MLE	Df Model:	2			
Date:	Sat, 02 May 2026	Pseudo R-squ.:	0.03756			
Time:	15:57:31	Log-Likelihood:	-106.24			
converged:	True	LL-Null:	-110.39			
Covariance Type:	nonrobust	LLR p-value:	0.01582			
	coef	std err	z	P> z 	[0.025	0.975]
const	1.5037	0.997	1.509	0.131	-0.449	3.457
Age	-0.0590	0.039	-1.493	0.135	-0.136	0.018
Gender_binary	-0.7828	0.327	-2.395	0.017	-1.423	-0.142

Table B.2: Model 2 - Job Preferences Model (Students, n = 163)

Logit Regression Results						
Dep. Variable:	PublicSectorIntent	No. Observations:	163			
Model:	Logit	Df Residuals:	158			
Method:	MLE	Df Model:	4			
Date:	Sat, 02 May 2026	Pseudo R-squ.:	0.08113			
Time:	15:57:31	Log-Likelihood:	-101.43			
converged:	True	LL-Null:	-110.39			
Covariance Type:	nonrobust	LLR p-value:	0.001285			
	coef	std err	z	P> z 	[0.025	0.975]
const	1.6217	1.014	1.600	0.110	-0.365	3.608
Age	-0.0643	0.040	-1.608	0.108	-0.143	0.014
Gender_binary	-0.8343	0.339	-2.459	0.014	-1.499	-0.169
SalaryIndex	0.4194	0.163	2.567	0.010	0.099	0.740
JobSecurityIndex	0.2072	0.165	1.254	0.210	-0.117	0.531

Table B.3: Model 3 - Full Model (Students, n = 163)

Logit Regression Results						
Dep. Variable:	PublicSectorIntent	No. Observations:	163			
Model:	Logit	Df Residuals:	156			
Method:	MLE	Df Model:	6			
Date:	Sat, 02 May 2026	Pseudo R-squ.:	0.1423			
Time:	15:57:31	Log-Likelihood:	-94.683			
converged:	True	LL-Null:	-110.39			
Covariance Type:	nonrobust	LLR p-value:	2.113e-05			
	coef	std err	z	P> z 	[0.025	0.975]
const	1.1044	1.029	1.073	0.283	-0.913	3.122
Age	-0.0459	0.040	-1.141	0.254	-0.125	0.033
Gender_binary	-0.8708	0.357	-2.436	0.015	-1.571	-0.170
SalaryIndex	0.4388	0.170	2.577	0.010	0.105	0.773
JobSecurityIndex	0.2582	0.174	1.487	0.137	-0.082	0.599
MotivationIndex	-0.3686	0.176	-2.095	0.036	-0.713	-0.024
LMM_Index	0.5989	0.193	3.103	0.002	0.221	0.977

Table B.4: Model 4 - Extended Model (Students, n = 163)

Logit Regression Results						
Dep. Variable:	PublicSectorIntent	No. Observations:	163			
Model:	Logit	Df Residuals:	153			
Method:	MLE	Df Model:	9			
Date:	Sat, 02 May 2026	Pseudo R-squ.:	0.2236			
Time:	15:57:31	Log-Likelihood:	-85.712			
converged:	True	LL-Null:	-110.39			
Covariance Type:	nonrobust	LLR p-value:	1.424e-07			
	coef	std err	z	P> z 	[0.025	0.975]
const	0.5056	1.109	0.456	0.648	-1.668	2.679
Age	-0.0257	0.043	-0.595	0.552	-0.110	0.059
Gender_binary	-0.9217	0.384	-2.401	0.016	-1.674	-0.169
SalaryIndex	0.2569	0.181	1.420	0.155	-0.098	0.611
JobSecurityIndex	0.3824	0.196	1.947	0.052	-0.003	0.767
MotivationIndex	-0.4274	0.190	-2.250	0.024	-0.800	-0.055
LMM_Index	0.6024	0.205	2.933	0.003	0.200	1.005
InnovationIndex	0.2187	0.187	1.172	0.241	-0.147	0.585
PrestigeIndex	0.5717	0.210	2.721	0.007	0.160	0.984
ExpectancyIndex	0.5107	0.206	2.477	0.013	0.107	0.915

Table B.5: Model 5 - Employment Outcome Model (Graduates, n = 149)

Logit Regression Results						
Dep. Variable:	PublicSectorEmployment No.	Observations:	149			
Model:	Logit	Df Residuals:	139			
Method:	MLE	Df Model:	9			
Date:	Sat, 02 May 2026	Pseudo R-squ.:	0.07271			
Time:	15:57:31	Log-Likelihood:	-95.517			
converged:	True	LL-Null:	-103.01			
Covariance Type:	nonrobust	LLR p-value:	0.09149			
	coef	std err	z	P> z 	[0.025	0.975]
const	0.0114	1.271	0.009	0.993	-2.479	2.502
Age	-0.0060	0.043	-0.140	0.889	-0.090	0.078
Gender_binary	0.6065	0.360	1.684	0.092	-0.099	1.312
SalaryIndex	-0.3687	0.203	-1.814	0.070	-0.767	0.030
JobSecurityIndex	0.0834	0.187	0.447	0.655	-0.282	0.449
MotivationIndex	-0.4678	0.196	-2.390	0.017	-0.852	-0.084
LMM_Index	-0.0539	0.181	-0.298	0.765	-0.408	0.300
InnovationIndex	0.0734	0.209	0.351	0.725	-0.336	0.483
PrestigeIndex	0.3447	0.212	1.629	0.103	-0.070	0.759
ExpectancyIndex	0.0238	0.188	0.127	0.899	-0.344	0.392

Table B.6: Average Marginal Effects – Model 1 (N = 163)

Basic Model – Marginal Effects (AME):						
	dy/dx	Std. Err.	z	Pr(> z)	Conf. Int. Low	\
Age	-0.013563	0.008859	-1.530976	0.125775	-0.030926	
Gender_binary	-0.180061	0.069944	-2.574372	0.010042	-0.317149	
	Cont. Int. Hi.					
Age	0.003800					
Gender_binary	-0.042974					

Table B.7: Average Marginal Effects – Model 2 (N = 163)

Preference Model – Marginal Effects (AME):						
	dy/dx	Std. Err.	z	Pr(> z)	Conf. Int. Low	\
Age	-0.013929	0.008409	-1.656476	0.097625	-0.030411	
Gender_binary	-0.180701	0.068346	-2.643911	0.008195	-0.314657	
SalaryIndex	0.090840	0.032713	2.776891	0.005488	0.026724	
JobSecurityIndex	0.044887	0.035178	1.275986	0.201961	-0.024061	
	Cont. Int. Hi.					
Age	0.002552					
Gender_binary	-0.046745					
SalaryIndex	0.154956					
JobSecurityIndex	0.113835					

Table B.8: Average Marginal Effects – Model 3 (N = 163)

Full Model – Marginal Effects (AME):						
	dy/dx	Std. Err.	z	Pr(> z)	Conf. Int.	Low \
Age	-0.009090	0.007841	-1.159181	0.246383	-0.024458	
Gender_binary	-0.172513	0.066085	-2.610483	0.009041	-0.302037	
SalaryIndex	0.086931	0.031210	2.785333	0.005347	0.025760	
JobSecurityIndex	0.051147	0.033623	1.521195	0.128211	-0.014753	
MotivationIndex	-0.073015	0.033137	-2.203457	0.027563	-0.137962	
LMM_Index	0.118650	0.034084	3.481108	0.000499	0.051847	
	Cont. Int.	Hi.				
Age		0.006279				
Gender_binary		-0.042989				
SalaryIndex		0.148102				
JobSecurityIndex		0.117048				
MotivationIndex		-0.008069				
LMM_Index		0.185453				

Table B.9: Average Marginal Effects – Model 4 (N = 163)

Extended Model – Marginal Effects (AME):						
	dy/dx	Std. Err.	z	Pr(> z)	Conf. Int.	Low \
Age	-0.004514	0.007547	-0.598167	0.549728	-0.019306	
Gender_binary	-0.161950	0.063222	-2.561612	0.010419	-0.285862	
SalaryIndex	0.045139	0.031022	1.455059	0.145653	-0.015663	
JobSecurityIndex	0.067196	0.033132	2.028154	0.042545	0.002259	
MotivationIndex	-0.075100	0.031441	-2.388575	0.016914	-0.136723	
LMM_Index	0.105844	0.032640	3.242830	0.001183	0.041872	
InnovationIndex	0.038431	0.032349	1.188020	0.234826	-0.024971	
PrestigeIndex	0.100455	0.034088	2.946960	0.003209	0.033644	
ExpectancyIndex	0.089734	0.033838	2.651835	0.008006	0.023412	
	Cont. Int.	Hi.				
Age		0.010277				
Gender_binary		-0.038037				
SalaryIndex		0.105941				
JobSecurityIndex		0.132134				
MotivationIndex		-0.013476				
LMM_Index		0.169817				
InnovationIndex		0.101833				
PrestigeIndex		0.167265				
ExpectancyIndex		0.156056				

Table B.10: Average Marginal Effects – Model 5 (N = 149)

Graduate Model – Marginal Effects (AME):						
	dy/dx	Std. Err.	z	Pr(> z)	Conf. Int.	Low \
Age	-0.001350	0.009646	-0.139924	0.888720	-0.020255	
Gender_binary	0.136558	0.078169	1.746955	0.080645	-0.016651	
SalaryIndex	-0.083017	0.043855	-1.892975	0.058361	-0.168971	
JobSecurityIndex	0.018780	0.041898	0.448227	0.653989	-0.063338	
MotivationIndex	-0.105341	0.040858	-2.578216	0.009931	-0.185421	
LMM_Index	-0.012137	0.040637	-0.298678	0.765186	-0.091783	
InnovationIndex	0.016522	0.046970	0.351762	0.725016	-0.075537	
PrestigeIndex	0.077609	0.046088	1.683939	0.092194	-0.012721	
ExpectancyIndex	0.005354	0.042300	0.126571	0.899280	-0.077553	
	Cont. Int.	Hi.				
Age		0.017555				
Gender_binary		0.289766				
SalaryIndex		0.002938				
JobSecurityIndex		0.100898				
MotivationIndex		-0.025261				
LMM_Index		0.067509				
InnovationIndex		0.108581				
PrestigeIndex		0.167940				
ExpectancyIndex		0.088261				